

A STUDY ON CRYPT ANALYSIS OF RSA

Dissertation

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the dissertation entitled " **A STUDY ON CRYPT ANALYSIS OF RSA**" submitted to Presidency College (Autonomous), Chennai-05, affiliated to University of Madras by **Elumalai R** a fulltime student of M.Phil., in the Department of Mathematics , Presidency College, Chennai - 05 for the award of the degree of Master of Philosophy in Mathematics is a record of bonafide work done by him during the period of study under my supervision and guidance and that not formed the basis for the award of any - research degree, diploma or other similar titles.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

In this thesis, we will discuss various cryptosystem. Particularly the scheme of RSA, its security, complexity, merits and demerits. And we will discuss various cryptanalytic attacks on *Prime Power RSA*.

1.1 Cryptography

Cryptography or *cryptology* is the practise and study of techniques for secure communication in the presence of third parties called adversaries. More generally, cryptography is about constructing and analysing protocols that prevent third parties or the public from reading private messages. Modern cryptography exists at the intersection of the disciplines of mathematics, computer science, and electrical engineering.

Cryptography prior to the modern age was effectively synonymous with encryption, the conversation of information from a readable state to apparent nonsense. *Al-kindī* wrote a book on cryptography entitled *Risalah fi Istikhraj al-Muamma*

which described the first known use of frequency analysis, cryptanalysis techniques. Basically, there are two types of cryptography: symmetric-key cryptography and public-key cryptography. Application: ATM cards, computer passwords, electronic commerce.

The message we want to send is called *plaintext* and the disguised message is called *ciphertext*.

Encryption: The process of converting a plaintext into ciphertext is called enciphering or encryption.

Decryption: The reverse process converting the ciphertext to plaintext, is called deciphering or decryption.

Cryptosystems: *Cryptosystems* is the ordered list of elements of finite possible plaintexts, finite possible ciphertexts, finite possible keys, and the encryption and decryption algorithms which correspond to each key.

Two kinds of cryptosystems:

- 1.Symmetric (same key)
- 2.Asymmetric (public key, private key)

Cryptanalysis: It is the term used for the study of methods for obtaining the meaning of encrypted information without access to the key normally required to do.

Cryptology: It refers to the combined study of *cryptography* and *cryptanalysis*.

1.1.1 Classic Cryptography

Rotor cipher machine in world war I plays a major role digital rights management and copyright infringement of digital media. *Enigma machine* used by the German government and military from the late 1920s and during World war II. *Steganography* include the use of invisible ink, microdots and digital Watermarks.

The main classical cipher types are transposition ciphers, which rearrange the order of letters in a message. EX: The *scytale transposition cipher* claimed to have been used by the Spartan military. An early substitution cipher was the **Caesar cipher**, in which each letter in the plaintext was replaced by a letter some fixed number of positions further down the alphabet. **Suetonius** reports that Julius Caesar used it with a shift of three to communicate with his generals.

1.1.2 Public Cryptography

In 1976, an asymmetric key cryptosystem was published by *Whitfield Diffie* and *Martin Hellman*. Public key cryptography, that uses pairs of keys: public keys which may be disseminated widely, and private keys which are known only to the owner. In a public key encryption system, any person can encrypt a message using the public key of the receiver, but such a message can be decrypted only with the receiver's private key. The strength of a public key cryptography system relies on the degree of difficulty for a properly generated private key to be determined from its corresponding public key.

1.2 The RSA Cryptosystem

The **RSA** public-key cryptosystem, invented by Ron **Rivest**, Adi **Shamir**, and Len **Adleman** [43], was first published in the August 1977 issue of *Scientific American*. The cryptosystem is most commonly used for providing privacy and ensuring authenticity of digital data. These days RSA is deployed in many commercial systems. It is used by Web servers and browsers to secure Web traffic, it is used to ensure privacy and authenticity of e-mail, it is used to secure remote login sessions,

and it is at the heart of electronic credit card payment systems. In short, RSA is frequently used in applications where security of digital data is a concern.

Since its initial publication, the RSA system has been analyzed for vulnerability by many researchers. Although twenty years of research have led to a number of fascinating attacks, none of them is devastating. They mostly illustrate the dangers of improper use of RSA. Indeed, securely implementing RSA is a non trivial task. Our goal is to discuss some of these attacks and describe the underlying mathematical tools they use. Throughout this thesis, we follow standard naming conventions and use *Alice* and *Bob* to denote two generic parties wishing to communicate with each other. We use *Marvin* to denote a malicious attacker wishing to eavesdrop or tamper with the communication between *Alice* and *Bob*.

We begin by describing a simplified version of RSA encryption. Let $N = pq$ be the product of two large primes of the same size ($\frac{k}{2}$ - bits each). A typical size for N is 1024 bits. i.e., 309 decimal digits.

Each of the factors is 512 bits. Let e, d be two integers satisfying $ed \equiv 1 \pmod{\phi(N)}$, where $\phi(N) = (p - 1)(q - 1)$ is the order of the multiplicative group \mathbb{Z}_N^* called *Euler totient function*. And $\psi(N)$ is defined as $\psi(N) = (p + 1)(q - 1)$, we discuss $\psi(N)$ later in chapter 2. We call N the RSA modulus, e the encryption exponent, and d the decryption exponent. The pair (N, e) is the public key. As its name suggests, it is public and is used to encrypt messages. The pair (N, d) is called the secret key or private key and is known only to the recipient of encrypted messages. The secret key enables decryption of ciphertexts.

A message is an integer $M \in \mathbb{Z}_N^*$. To encrypt M , one computes $C \equiv M^e \pmod{N}$. To decrypt the ciphertext, the legitimate receiver computes $C^d \pmod{N}$. Indeed,

$$C^d \equiv M^{ed} \equiv M^{1+k\phi(N)} \equiv M.M^{k\phi(N)} \equiv M.(M^{\phi(N)})^k \equiv M \pmod{N}.$$

where the last equality follows by *Eulers theorem*. One defines the RSA function as $x \rightarrow x^e \bmod N$. If d is given, the function can be easily inverted using the above equality. We refer to d as a trapdoor enabling one to invert the function. We study the difficulty of inverting the RSA function without the trapdoor. We refer to this as breaking RSA. More precisely, given the triple (N, e, C) , we ask how hard is it to compute the e^{th} root of $C \bmod N$ when the factorization of N is unknown. Since \mathbb{Z}_N^* is a finite set, one may enumerate all elements of \mathbb{Z}_N^* until the correct M is found. Unfortunately, this results in an algorithm with running time of order N , namely, exponential in the size of its input, which is of the order $\log_2 N$. We are interested mostly in algorithms with a substantially lower running time, namely, on the order of n^c where $n = \log_2 N$ and c is some small constant (less than 5, say). Such algorithms often perform well in practice on the inputs in question. Throughout this thesis we refer to such algorithms as efficient.

We mainly study the RSA function as opposed to the RSA Cryptosystem. Loosely speaking, the difficulty of inverting the RSA function on random inputs implies that given (N, e, C) , an attacker cannot recover the plaintext M . However, a cryptosystem must resist more susceptible attacks. If (N, e, C) is given, it should be intractable to recover any information about M . This is known as semantic security. We do not discuss these susceptible attacks, but point out that RSA as described above is not semantically secure: given (N, e, C) , one can easily deduce some information about the plaintext M (for instance, the Jacobi symbol of M over N can be easily deduced from C). RSA can be made semantically secure by adding randomness to the encryption process.

The RSA function $x \rightarrow x^e \bmod N$ is an example of a trapdoor one-way function. It can be easily computed, but (as far as we know) cannot be efficiently inverted without the trapdoor d except in special circumstances. Trapdoor one-way

functions can be used for digital signatures. Digital signatures provide authenticity and nonrepudiation of electronic legal documents. For instance, they are used for signing digital checks or electronic purchase orders. To sign a message $M \in \mathbb{Z}_N^*$ using RSA, *Alice* applies her private key (N, d) to M and obtains a signature $S \equiv M^d \bmod N$. Given (M, S) , anyone can verify *Alice's* signature on M by checking that $S^e \equiv M \bmod N$. Since only *Alice* can generate S , one may suspect that an adversary cannot forge *Alice's* signature. Digital signatures are an important application of RSA.

An RSA key pair is generated by picking two random $\frac{k}{2}$ -bit primes and multiplying them to obtain N . Then, for a given encryption exponent $e < \phi(N)$, one computes $d \equiv e^{-1} \bmod \phi(N)$ using the extended Euclidean algorithm. Since the set of primes is sufficiently dense, a random $\frac{k}{2}$ -bit prime can be quickly generated by repeatedly picking random $\frac{k}{2}$ -bit integers and testing each one for primality using a *probabilistic primality test*.

We describe five constituent algorithms: key generation, encryption, decryption, signature and signature verification. Below we describe in detail the initial schemes of the RSA Cryptosystem.

RSA Key Generation

INPUT : The bitsize k of the modulus.

OUTPUT : A public key (N, e) and a private key (N, d) .

1. Generate two large random and distinct $(\frac{k}{2})$ -bit primes p and q .
2. Compute $N = pq$ and $\phi(N) = (p - 1)(q - 1)$.
3. Choose a random integer e such that $3 \leq e < \phi(N)$
and $\gcd(e, \phi(N)) = 1$.

4. Compute the unique integer d such that $1 \leq d < \phi(N)$ and $ed \equiv 1 \pmod{\phi(N)}$.
5. Return the public key (N, e) and the private key (N, d) .

RSA Encryption

INPUT : The public key (N, e) and the plaintext \mathbf{m} .

OUTPUT : The ciphertext C .

1. Represent the message \mathbf{m} as an integer M with $1 \leq M \leq N - 1$.
2. Compute $C \equiv M^e \pmod{N}$.
3. Return the ciphertext C .

RSA Decryption

INPUT : The private key (N, d) and the ciphertext C .

OUTPUT : The message \mathbf{m} .

1. Compute $M \equiv C^d \pmod{N}$.
2. Transform the number M to the message \mathbf{m} .
3. Return the message \mathbf{m} .

Algorithm	Encryption Speed	Decryption Speed
RSA	$O(n^2)$	$O(n^3)$
ECC	$O(n^3)$	$O(n^3)$

Table 1: Algorithm complexity

1.2.1 Prime Power RSA Cryptosystem

In Prime Power RSA the modulus N is in the form $N = p^r q$ for $r \geq 2$.

Modulus size(bits)	1024	1536	2048	3072
Form of the modulus N	pq, p^2q	pq, p^2q	pq, p^2q	pq, p^2q
	4096	8192		
	pq, p^2q, p^3q	pq, p^2q, p^3q, p^4q		

1.3 Insecure RSA

The RSA cryptosystem is a well-known asymmetric cryptosystem for transmission of data [42]. Basically, the difficulty of breaking the RSA Cryptosystem is based on three hard mathematical problems: (i) *The integer factorization problem of $N = pq$* , (ii) *The e^{th} root problem from $C \equiv M^e \pmod{N}$* and (iii) *To solve the Diophantine key equation $ed - 1 \equiv \phi(N)k$* .

The encryption and decryption processes in RSA require executing exponential multiplications modulo the integer $N = pq$. To reduce the encryption time, one may wish to use a small public exponent e , while to reduce the decryption time, one may be tempted to use a short secret exponent d . The choice of small d is especially interesting when the device performing secret operations has limited power.

To speed up the RSA decryption of some devices with limited computing power such as smart card, one might be tempted to use short secret exponents d . In 1990, *Wiener* [49] showed that if $d < \frac{1}{3}N^{.25}$, then RSA was insecure. *Wiener's* method is based on approximations using continued fractions. *Verheul* and *Van Tilborg* [47] and *Dujella* [15] proposed an extension of the results of *Wiener* that allows RSA to be broken when $d < N^{\frac{1}{4}+\gamma}$ using an exhaustive search for about $8 + 2\gamma \log_2 N$ bit. In 1999, *Boneh* and *Durfee* [9][7] improved *Wiener's* bound to

$d < N^{0.292}$ [9]. Their attack is based on *Coppersmiths technique* for finding small roots to polynomial equations, which in turn is based on the LLL-lattice reduction algorithm. In 2002, *de Weger* [48] proposed an extension of these attacks to an RSA modulus with a small difference between its prime factors. In 2004, *Blömer* and *May* [4] extended both *Wiener* and *de Weger* attacks for the RSA Cryptosystems with secret exponents having the modular factorization $d \equiv -xy^{-1}(\text{mod } \phi(N))$ where x and y are integers satisfying $1 \leq x < \frac{1}{3}N^{\frac{1}{4}}$ and $|y| < N^{\frac{3}{4}}ex$.

Moreover, they showed that the number of such keys is at least $O\left(N^{\frac{3}{4}} - \epsilon\right)$ where ϵ is a positive constant. In contrast to the attacks of *Wiener* and *Boneh-Durfee*, the secret key in the attack of *Blömer-May* could be large.

Let $N = pq$ be an *RSA* modulus with $q < p < 2q$. Suppose we know an approximation p_0 of p with $|p - p_0| < \frac{1}{8}N^\alpha$. In 2008, *Nassar et al.* presented a continued fraction attack on RSA with a private exponent satisfying $d < N^{\frac{1-\alpha}{2}}$.

Later, *Howgrave-Graham* and *Seifert* proposed an extension of *Wieners* attack that allows the RSA system to be insecure in the presence of two decryption exponents (d_1, d_2) with $d_1, d_2 < N^{5/14}$. In the presence of three decryption exponents, they improved the bound to $N^{2/5}$ based on lattice reduction method. In 2007, *Hinek* showed that it is possible to factor the k modulus N_i using equations $e_i x - y_i \phi(N_i) = 1$ if $d < N^\delta$ with $\delta = \frac{k}{2(k+1)} - \epsilon$ where ϵ is a small constant depending on the size of $\max N_i$.

In 2014, *Nitaj et al.* presented new method to factor all the RSA moduli N_1, \dots, N_k in the scenario that RSA instances satisfy k equations of the shape $e_i x - y_i \phi(N_i) = z_i$ or of the shape $e_i x_i - y_i \phi(N_i) = z_i$ with suitable parameters x, x_i, y, y_i and $z_i, \phi(N_i) = (p_i - 1)(q_i - 1)$ based on the LLL algorithm which has been introduced by *Lenstra et al.*[29] for lattice basis reduction [40].

In [46] *Takagi* (1997) showed how to use the Prime Power RSA to speed up the decryption process when the public and private exponents satisfy an equation $ed \equiv (\text{mod } (p-1)(q-1))$. *Okamoto* and *Uchiyama* (1998) presented a public key cryptosystem that is provably as secure as factoring a modulus in the form $N = p^2q$ [41].

In 1999, *Bonech*, *Durfee*, and *Howgrave-Graham* [8] presented a method for factoring $N = p^r q$ when r is large. Furthermore, *Takagi* [46] proved that one can factor N if $d < N^{\frac{1}{2(r+1)}}$. In 2004, *May* [32] improved the bound of private exponent to $d < N^{\frac{r}{(r+1)^2}}$ for RSA modulus in the form $N = p^r q$ [32]. Very recently, *Lu*, *Zhang* and *Lin* [30] improved the bound to $d < N^{\frac{r(r-1)}{(r+1)^2}}$. Later, *Sarkar* [45] (2014) improved the bound to $d < N^{0.395}$ for RSA modulus $N = p^2q$ and gave explicit bounds for $r = 3, 4, 5$.

Recently, *Asbullah* and *Ariffin* showed that one can factor $N = p^2q$ in polynomial time if e satisfies the equation $eX - (N - (ap^2 + bq^2))Y = Z$ where a, b are positive integers satisfying $\gcd(a, b) = 1$, $|ap^2 - bq^2| < N^{1/2}$,

$$|Z| < \frac{|ap^2 - bq^2|}{3(ap^2 + bq^2)} N^{1/3} Y$$

and

$$1 \leq Y \leq X < \frac{N^{1/2}}{2(ap^2 + bq^2)^{1/2}}$$

[3]. Moreover, throughout this thesis we assume that the primes p and q are balanced, in other words, that the bit sizes of the primes are equal so that $q < p < 2q$.

Figure 1: Upper bound of various attack

1.4 Factoring Large Integers

The first attack on an RSA public key (N, e) is factoring the modulus N . Given the factorization of N , an attacker can easily construct $\phi(N)$, from which the decryption exponent $d \equiv e^{-1} \pmod{\phi(N)}$ can be found. We refer to factoring the modulus as a *brute-force* attack on RSA. Although factoring algorithms have been steadily improving, the current state of the art is still far from posing a threat to the security of RSA when RSA is used properly. The current fastest factoring algorithm is the *General Number Field Sieve* [35] for factoring numbers that are at or beyond the current (1994) upper limits of what can be factored, i.e., > 150 digits. Its running time on n -bit integers is $\exp((c + o(1))n^{\frac{1}{3}} \log^{\frac{2}{3}} n)$ for some $c < 2$. It is perhaps the most complicated factoring algorithm known. The basic requirements of the algorithm can be briefly described as follows. Given an integer n to be factored, choose a degree d and find n as the value at some integer m of an irreducible monic

integer polynomial of degree d :

$$n = f(m) = m^d + a_{d-1}m^{d-1} + \dots + a_1m + a_0,$$

where m and the a_k are integers that are $O(n^{\frac{1}{d}})$. One way to find such a polynomial is to let m be the integer part of the d -th root of n and then expand n to the base m . For 125-digit numbers an analysis of the algorithm suggests that d should be 5, so that m and the coefficients will have about 25 digits. The number field sieve then searches (by a sieving process similar to the quadratic sieve) for as many pairs (a, b) as possible such that both $a + bm$ and also

$$b^d f(-a/b) = (-a)^d + a_{d-1}(-a)^{d-1}b + a_{d-2}(-a)^{d-2}b^2 + \dots + a_1(-a)b^{d-1} + a_0b^d$$

are smooth over a given factor base (i.e., are divisible only by primes in the factor base). Attacks on RSA that take longer than this time bound are not interesting. These include attacks such as an exhaustive search for M and some older attacks published right after the initial publication of RSA. Our objective is to discuss attacks on RSA that decrypt messages without directly factoring the RSA modulus N . Nevertheless, it is worth noting that some sparse sets of RSA moduli, $N = pq$, can be easily factored. For instance, if $p - 1$ is a product of prime factors less than B , then N can be factored in time less than B^3 . Some implementations explicitly reject primes p for which $p - 1$ is a product of small primes. As noted above, if an efficient factoring algorithm exists, then RSA is insecure.

1.5 Continued Fractions Expansion

A continued fraction is an expression of the form

$$a_0 + \frac{1}{a_1 + \frac{1}{\ddots + \frac{1}{a_n + \ddots}}}} = [a_0, a_1, \dots, a_n, \dots],$$

where a_0 is an integer and a_n are positive integers for $n \geq 1$. Then a_n are called the partial quotients of the continued fraction. It is clear that every finite continued fraction defines a rational number. Conversely, every real number $x \neq 0$ can be expanded as a finite or infinite continued fraction by the continued fraction algorithm as follows. Let $\lfloor x \rfloor$ denote the greatest integer less than or equal to x . Let $x_0 = x$ and $a_0 = \lfloor x_0 \rfloor$. Then, for $i \geq 0$, define

$$x_{i+1} = \frac{1}{x_i - a_i}, a_{i+1} = \lfloor x_{i+1} \rfloor.$$

The procedure terminates only if $a_i = x_i$ for some $i \geq 0$, that is if x is a rational number. The continued fraction of a rational number $x = \frac{a}{b}$ with $\gcd(a, b) = 1$ can be computed by the Euclidean Algorithm in time $O(\log^3 b)$. Set $r_0 = a$ and $r_1 = b$. For $i \geq 0$, divide r_i by r_{i+1} :

$$r_i = a_i r_{i+1} + r_{i+2}, 0 \leq r_{i+2} < r_{i+1}$$

This process stops when $r_{m+2} = 0$ for some $m \geq 0$. In 1990, *Wiener* proposed an attack on RSA with modulus N and small private exponent d . The attack is based on the convergence of the continued fraction expansion of $\frac{e}{N}$. which, for simplicity, can be rewritten as $x = [a_0, a_1, \dots, a_n, \dots]$. If x is a rational number, then the process of calculating the continued fractions expansion will finish in some finite index n and then $x = [a_0, a_1, \dots, a_n]$. The convergence $\frac{a}{b}$ of x are the fractions denoted by $\frac{a}{b} = [a_0, a_1, \dots, a_i]$ for $i \geq 0$.

1.6 Lattice Basis Reductions

Let u_1, \dots, u_d be d linearly independent vectors of R^n with $d \leq n$. The set of all integer linear combinations of the vectors u_1, \dots, u_d is called a lattice and is in the form

$L = \left(\sum_{i=1}^d x_i u_i \mid x_i \in \mathbb{Z} \right)$ The set (u_1, \dots, u_d) is called a basis of L and d is its dimension. The determinant of L is defined as $\det(L) = \sqrt{\det(UTU)}$ where U is the matrix of the u_i s in the canonical basis of R^n . Define $\|v\|$ to be the Euclidean norm of a vector $v \in L$. A central problem in lattice reduction is to find a short non-zero vector in L . The *Lenstra-Lenstra-Lovasz* algorithm (LLL algorithm) produces [29] a reduced basis.

Chapter 2

RSA with modulus $N = pq$

The RSA system is the best known and most widely accepted public key cryptosystem. RSA is most commonly used for providing privacy and ensuring authenticity of digital data. It is used in several operating systems, like Microsoft, Apple and Sun. It is also used for securing Web traffic, e-mail and smart cards. The main attacks on RSA include attacks on the modulus, low private and public exponent attacks.

In this chapter, we present (i) the *Wiener's attack* and *de Weger's generalization of Wiener's attack* using Diophantine approximations, (ii) *Bonech and Durfee's class of weak keys* using lattice method (iii) *Blömer and May's class of weak keys* using continued fractions and Coppersmith's lattice based technique, (iv) the *Generalised Wiener attack* using continued fractions and Coppersmith's theorem.

Definition 1. (*LLL Reduction*) Let $B = \langle b_1, \dots, b_n \rangle$ be a basis for a lattice ζ and $B^* = \langle b_1^*, \dots, b_n^* \rangle$ be the associated Gram-Schmidt orthogonal basis. Let

$$\mu_{i,j} = \frac{\langle b_i, b_j^* \rangle}{\langle b_j^*, b_j^* \rangle} \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq i$$

The basis B is said to be LLL reduced if it satisfies the following two conditions:

$$|\mu_{i,j}| \leq \frac{1}{2} \text{ for } 1 \leq j < i \leq n,$$

$$\frac{3}{4} \|b_{i-1}^*\|^2 \leq \|b_i^* + \mu_{i,i-1} b_{i-1}^*\|^2 \text{ for } 1 < i \leq n.$$

An important result on continued fractions that will be used is the following theorem.

Theorem 1. (Legendre)[16] Let ξ be a real number. If the coprime integers k and d satisfy

$$\left| \xi - \frac{k}{d} \right| < \frac{1}{2d^2}$$

then $\frac{k}{d}$ is a convergent of ξ .

2.1 Wiener's Attack on RSA

A well-known attack on RSA with low secret-exponent d was given by Wiener [49] in 1990. Wiener showed that using continued fractions, one can efficiently recover the secret exponent d from the public key (N, e) as long as $d < \frac{1}{3}N^{\frac{1}{4}}$.

Theorem 2. (Wiener) Let $N = pq$ with $q < p < 2q$. Let $d < \frac{1}{3}N^{\frac{1}{4}}$. Given (N, e) with $ed \equiv 1 \pmod{\phi(N)}$, Marvin can efficiently recover d .

Proof. This is based on approximations using continued fractions. Since

$$ed \equiv 1 \pmod{\phi(N)},$$

there exists a k such that $ed - k\phi(N) = 1$. Therefore

$$\left| \frac{e}{\phi(N)} - \frac{k}{d} \right| = \frac{1}{d\phi(N)}.$$

Hence, $\frac{k}{d}$ is an approximation of $\frac{e}{\phi(N)}$. Although the attacker does not know $\phi(N)$, he may use N to approximate it. Indeed, since $\phi(N) = N - p - q + 1$ We have :

$$\begin{aligned} p + q - 1 &< 3\sqrt{N} \\ N + 1 - \phi(N) - 1 &< 3\sqrt{N} \end{aligned}$$

Using N in place of $\phi(N)$ we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \frac{e}{\phi(N)} - \frac{k}{d} \right| &= \left| \frac{ed - kN}{Nd} \right| \\ &= \left| \frac{ed - k\phi(N) - kN + k\phi(N)}{Nd} \right| \\ &\leq \left| \frac{3k\sqrt{N}}{Nd} \right| \\ &= \frac{3k\sqrt{N}}{\sqrt{N}\sqrt{Nd}} \\ &= \frac{3k}{\sqrt{N}} \end{aligned}$$

Now $k\phi(N) = ed - 1$ so $k\phi(N) < ed$. Since $e < \phi(N)$ then $k\phi(N) < ed < \phi(N)d$. Therefore we obtain $k\phi(N) < \phi(N)d$, $k < d$ Since $k < d$ and $d < \frac{1}{3}N^{\frac{1}{4}}$, hence we obtain

$$\left| \frac{e}{N} - \frac{k}{d} \right| \leq \frac{1}{dN^{\frac{1}{4}}}.$$

Since $d < \frac{1}{3}N^{\frac{1}{4}}$, $2d < 3d$ then $2d < 3d < N^{\frac{1}{4}}$.

Hence $2d < N^{\frac{1}{4}}$. Thus

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2d} &> \frac{1}{N^{\frac{1}{4}}} \\ \left| \frac{e}{N} - \frac{k}{d} \right| &\leq \frac{3k}{d\sqrt{N}} \\ &< \frac{1}{d \cdot 2d} \\ &= \frac{1}{2d^2}. \end{aligned}$$

This is a classic approximation relation. The number of fractions $\frac{k}{d}$ with $d < N$ approximating $\frac{e}{N}$ so closely is bounded by $\log_2 N$. In fact, all such fractions are obtained as convergence of the continued fraction expansion of $\frac{e}{N}$. All one has to do is compute the $\log N$ convergence of the continued fraction for $\frac{e}{N}$. One of these will equal $\frac{k}{d}$. Since $ed - k\phi(N) = 1$, we have $\gcd(k, d) = 1$, and hence $\frac{k}{d}$ is a reduced fraction. This is a linear-time algorithm for recovering the secret key d . Since typically N is 1024 bits, it follows that d must be at least 256 bits long in order to avoid this attack. This is unfortunate for low-power devices such as smartcards, where a small d would result in big savings. All is not lost however. *Wiener* describes a number of techniques that enable fast decryption and are not susceptible to his attack:

Since Diophantine key equation is $ed \equiv 1 \pmod{\phi(N)}$, then $ed - k\phi(N) = 1$. We have $\phi(N) = \frac{ed-1}{k}$. since the convergent $\frac{k}{d}$ of the continued fraction $\frac{e}{N}$ is known, then $\phi(N)$ can be obtained. Solving the quadratic equation

$$x^2 - (N - \phi(N) + 1)x + N = 0,$$

the solution becomes p and q . Therefore N is factored in polynomial time.

□

For $N = pq$ with $q < p < 2q$, we present below *Wiener's* attack on RSA which works for the bound $d < \frac{\sqrt{6\sqrt{2}}}{6} \geq \frac{1}{3} + 0.15$.

Lemma 1. *Let $N = pq$ be an RSA modulus with $q < p < 2q$. Then*

$$\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}\sqrt{N} < q < \sqrt{N} < p < \sqrt{2}\sqrt{N}$$

and

$$2\sqrt{N} < p + q < \frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}\sqrt{N}.$$

Proof. Suppose $q < p < 2q$. Multiplying by q , we get $q^2 < N < 2q^2$. Hence

$$\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}\sqrt{N} < q < \sqrt{N}.$$

Using $p = \frac{N}{q}$, we get $\sqrt{N} < p < \sqrt{2}\sqrt{N}$. This proves the first assertion.

To prove the second one, observe that

$$(p + q)^2 = (p - q)^2 + 4N > 4N,$$

which gives $p + q > 2\sqrt{N}$. On the other hand, we have

$$(p + q)^2 = (p - q)^2 + 4N < \left(\sqrt{2}\sqrt{N} - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}\sqrt{N} \right)^2 + 4N = \frac{9}{2}N.$$

Hence

$$p + q < \frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}\sqrt{N}.$$

□

Theorem 3. (*Wiener*). *Let $N = pq$ be an RSA modulus with $q < p < 2q$. Let $e < \phi(N)$ be a public exponent and d be the corresponding private key. If $d < \frac{\sqrt{6\sqrt{2}}}{6}N^{\frac{1}{4}}$, then, we can find the factorisation of N in time polynomial in $\log N$.*

Proof. We write the equation $ed - k(N + 1 - p - q) = 1$ as $ed - kN = 1 - k(p + q - 1)$.

Dividing by Nd , we get

$$\left| \frac{e}{N} - \frac{k}{d} \right| = \frac{|1 - k(p + q - 1)|}{Nd} < \frac{k(p + q - 1)}{Nd}. \quad (2.1)$$

Since $e < \phi(N)$, then

$$k = \frac{ed - 1}{\phi(N)} < \frac{ed}{\phi(N)} < d.$$

Hence (2.1) gives

$$\left| \frac{e}{N} - \frac{k}{d} \right| < \frac{k(p + q - 1)}{N} < \frac{p + q}{N}$$

using Lemma 1, this implies

$$\left| \frac{e}{N} - \frac{k}{d} \right| < \frac{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}\sqrt{N}}{N} < \frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}\sqrt{N}.$$

Suppose that

$$d < \frac{6\sqrt{2}}{6}N^{-\frac{1}{2}},$$

then

$$\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}N^{-\frac{1}{2}} < \frac{1}{2d^2}$$

and consequently

$$\left| \frac{e}{N} - \frac{k}{d} \right| < \frac{1}{2d^2}.$$

Hence the theorem 1 gives $\frac{k}{d}$ as a convergent of the continued fraction expansion of $\frac{e}{N}$. But the continued fraction algorithm is polynomial time in $\log N$. \square

Legendres theorem and Coppersmiths technique

In this section we briefly recall Coppersmiths lattice method and the classical Legendres theorem on diophantine approximations. Let $N = pq$ be an RSA modulus with $q < p < 2q$. Let $f(x)$ be an univariate monic polynomial of degree δ . In [13] Coppersmith described a remarkable method that finds all integer solutions

x_0 of the equation $f(x_0) \equiv 0 \pmod{N}$ provided that $|x_0| \leq \frac{1}{2}N^{\frac{1}{8}\epsilon}$. This method has many applications in cryptography. A key role in our attack is played by the following theorem (see [13] or [31]).

Theorem 4. (Coppersmith) *Let $N = pq$ be an RSA modulus with $q < p < 2q$. If \tilde{p} is an approximation of p satisfying $|p - \tilde{p}| \leq 2N^{\frac{1}{4}}$ then N can be factored in polynomial time in $\log N$.*

2.2 The Generalized Wiener attack

We consider RSA-moduli $N = pq$, where p and q are of the same bit-size ($w \log p > q$). This implies the inequalities

$$p - q \leq N^{\frac{1}{2}} \text{ and } 2N^{\frac{1}{2}} \leq p + q \leq 3N^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

Furthermore, we have $\phi(N) = N + 1 - (p + q) > \frac{N}{2}$. Our attack makes use of a well-known result due to Coppersmith.

Theorem 5. *Let $N = pq$ be an RSA-modulus, where p and q are of the same bit-size. Suppose we are given an approximation of p with additive error at most $N^{\frac{1}{4}}$. Then N can be factored in time polynomial in $\log N$.*

Theorem 6. *Let $c \leq 1$ and let (N, e) be an RSA public key tuple with $N = pq$ and $p - q \geq cN^{\frac{1}{2}}$. Suppose that $e \in \mathbb{Z}_{\phi(N)}^*$ satisfies an equation $ex + y = k\phi(N)$ with*

$$0 < x \leq \frac{1}{3}N^{\frac{1}{4}} \text{ and } |y| \leq cN^{-\frac{3}{4}}ex.$$

Then N can be factored in polynomial time.

One should notice that the conditions of above Theorem imply that $ex + y \neq 0$, thereby excluding trivial congruences: Since $c \leq 1$, we see that $|y| < ex$. This is

in turn implies $k > 0$.

Roadmap for the proof of the above Theorem

- We show that the unknown parameters x, k can be found among the convergence of the continued fraction expansion of $\frac{e}{N}$
- From x and k , we compute an approximation of $p + q$.
- From an approximation of $p + q$, we compute an approximation of $p - q$.
- Combining both approximations gives us an approximation of p , which leads to the factorization of N by using *Coppersmith's Theorem*.

We want to argue that in the following proof we can assume wlog that $N \geq (\frac{8}{c})^4$. This condition is equivalent to $c \geq 8N^{-\frac{1}{4}}$. If this inequality does not hold then $p - q = O(N^{\frac{1}{4}})$ and *Fermat's factorization algorithm* yields the factorization of N in polynomial time.

Proof. Let us start with the RSA key equation

$$ex + y = k(N - p - q + 1).$$

Dividing by Nx gives us

$$\frac{e}{N} - \frac{k}{x} = -\frac{k(p + q - 1) + y}{Nx}. \quad (2.2)$$

We want to argue that we can assume wlog that $\gcd(k, x) = 1$. Notice that every integer that divides both k and x must also divide y by equation (2.2). Thus, we can divide equation (2.2) by $\gcd(k, x)$ which gives us an equation $ex' + y' = 0 \pmod{\phi(N)}$ with even smaller parameters x' and y' . Hence we can assume that $\frac{k}{x}$ is a fraction in its lowest terms.

By a well-known theorem 1, the fraction $\frac{k}{x}$ appears among the convergence of $\frac{e}{N}$ if the condition $|\frac{e}{N} - \frac{k}{x}| < \frac{1}{2x^2}$ is satisfied. Thus it remains to show that

$|k(p + q - 1)| < \frac{N}{2x}$. Let us first find a bound for the parameter k . We know that $k = \frac{ex+y}{\phi(N)}$ and $|y| \leq cN^{-\frac{3}{4}}ex$. Since our precondition $N \geq (\frac{8}{c})^4$ implies $N \geq 2^{12}$, we conclude that $|y| \leq \frac{1}{4}ex$. Therefore, we obtain

$$\frac{3}{4} \frac{ex}{\phi(N)} \leq k \leq \frac{5}{4} \frac{ex}{\phi(N)}.$$

Now we are able to estimate

$$k(p + q - 1) + y \leq \frac{15}{4} \frac{ex}{\phi(N)} N^{\frac{1}{2}} + cN^{-\frac{3}{4}}ex \leq \frac{15}{4} xN^{\frac{1}{2}} + xN^{\frac{1}{4}} \leq 4xN^{\frac{1}{2}},$$

where the last inequality holds for $N \geq 2^{12}$. Therefore, we have to satisfy the condition $4xN^{\frac{1}{2}} < \frac{N}{2x}$ which is equivalent to $x < \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}N^{\frac{1}{4}}$. This condition holds by our upper bound $x \leq \frac{1}{3}N^{\frac{1}{4}}$. Hence, the fraction $\frac{k}{x}$ must be among the convergence of the continued fraction expansion of $\frac{e}{N}$. Since there are only $O(\log N)$ many convergence, we can apply the following process to each candidate for k and x until our algorithm succeeds. We have to show that the correct k and x yield the factorization of N . Let us write equation (2.2) as

$$N + 1 - \frac{ex}{k} = p + q + \frac{y}{k}.$$

Since every parameter on the left hand side is now known to us, we can compute an approximation of $p + q$ up to some unknown error term $\frac{y}{k}$, that can be bounded by $|y| \leq \frac{4}{3}cN^{\frac{1}{4}}$ using inequality.

Our goal is to find an approximation of p up to some error of size $N^{\frac{1}{4}}$ in order to apply *Coppersmith's theorem*. Therefore, we transform our approximation of $p + q$ into an approximation of $p - q$ using the relation

$$p - q = \sqrt{(p - q)^2} = \sqrt{(p + q)^2 - 4N}.$$

Let s be our approximation of $p + q$ with additive error at most $\frac{4}{3}cN^{\frac{1}{4}}$. We will show that $t = \sqrt{s^2 - 4N}$ is an approximation of $p - q$ with an additive error that can be

bounded by $9N^{\frac{1}{4}}$. Thus, the term $\frac{1}{2}(s+t)$ is an approximation of p with error at most.

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \frac{1}{2}(s+t) - p \right| &= \frac{1}{2} |s - p - q + t - p + q| \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2} |s - (p+q)| + \frac{1}{2} |t - (p-q)| \\ &\leq \frac{2}{3} cN^{\frac{1}{4}} + \frac{9}{2} \leq 6N^{\frac{1}{4}}. \end{aligned}$$

Define $\tilde{p} = \frac{1}{2}(s+t)$. Then one out of the six values $\tilde{p} + (2k+1)N^{\frac{1}{4}}$, $k = -3, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2$ is an approximation of p upto an error of at most $N^{\frac{1}{4}}$ in absolute value. We can apply Coppersmith's algorithm to all these values. The correct term will then lead to the factorization of N in polynomial time.

It remains to show that $t = \sqrt{s^2 - 4N}$ is indeed an approximation of $p - q$ upto some error term that can be bounded by $9N^{\frac{1}{4}}$. Let us first show that t is well-defined, ie. $s^2 - 4N \geq 0$. Observe that $s = p + q + \frac{y}{k}$ satisfies

$$s^2 - 4N = (p - q)^2 + 2\frac{y}{k}(p + q) + \left(\frac{y}{k}\right)^2.$$

Therefore, it suffices to show that $|2\frac{y}{k}(p + q)| \leq (p - q)^2$. Using $|\frac{y}{k}| \leq \frac{4}{3}cN^{\frac{1}{4}}$, we obtain $|2\frac{y}{k}(p + q)| \leq 8cN^{\frac{3}{4}}$. From our precondition $N \geq (\frac{8}{c})^4$, we see that $8 \leq cN^{\frac{1}{4}}$. This immediately implies $8cN^{\frac{3}{4}} \leq c^2N \leq (p - q)^2$ as desired. Since $N \geq 2^{12}$, we know that the error term $\frac{y}{k}$ for $p + q$ can be bounded in absolute value by $\frac{3}{4}cN^{\frac{1}{4}} \leq \frac{1}{2}N^{\frac{1}{2}} \leq \frac{1}{4}(p + q)$. This implies the inequality

$$s \leq \frac{5}{4}(p + q).$$

We observe that

$$t - (p - q) = \sqrt{s^2 - 4N} - (p - q) = \frac{(s - (p - q))(s + (p - q))}{\sqrt{s^2 - 4N} + (p - q)}.$$

Using the inequalities , $s - (p + q) \leq \frac{4}{3}cN^{\frac{1}{4}}$ and $p - q \geq cN^{\frac{1}{4}}$ finally leads us to the desired bound

$$t - (p - q) \leq \frac{\frac{4}{3}cN^{\frac{1}{4}} \frac{27}{4}N^{\frac{1}{2}}}{(p - q)} \leq 9N^{\frac{1}{4}}.$$

□

Let us briefly summarize the whole factorization algorithm.

Algorithm Generalised Wiener Attack
<p>INPUT : (N, e), where $N = pq$ and $ex + y = 0 \pmod{\phi(N)}$ for some unknown $0 < x \leq \frac{1}{3}N^{\frac{1}{4}}$ and $y \leq cN^{-\frac{3}{4}}ex$.</p> <p>OUTPUT: p, q</p>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Compute the continued fraction expansion of $\frac{e}{N}$ 2. For every convergent $\frac{k}{x}$ of the expansion: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (a) Compute $s = N + 1 - \frac{ex}{N}$, $t = \sqrt{s^2 - 4N}$ and $\tilde{p} = \frac{1}{2}(s + t)$. (b) Apply Coppersmith's algorithm to the candidates $\tilde{p} + (2k + 1)N^{\frac{1}{4}}$ for $k = -3, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2$: If Coppersmith's algorithm outputs the factorization of N, then stop.

Table 2 : Algorithm 1

2.3 Bonech and Durfee's Class of Weak Keys

In 1999, *Bonech* and *Durfee* [9] introduced the small inverse problem and presented a substantial improvement over *Wiener's* bound. Their attack can recover the primes p, q in polynomial time provided that $d < N^{0.292}$. Their result is based on Coppersmith's technic for finding small solutions to modular polynomial equations. We present a weaker result which is valid for $d < N^{0.284}$.

Theorem 7. *Let $N = pq$ be an RSA modulus with $q < p < 2q$. Let $e < \phi(N)$ be a public exponent and d be the corresponding private exponent. If $d < N^{0.284}$, then, we can find the factorization of N in time polynomial in $\log N$.*

Proof. Starting with the equation $ed - k\phi(N) = 1$, we get $k(N + 1 - p - q) + 1 = ed$ which leads to the modular equation $x(A + y) + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{e}$, where $A = N + 1$. This is an inverse problem with the solution $(k, -p - q)$. Suppose $e < \phi(N)$ is of the same order of magnitude as N , that is $e \approx N$. If $d < N^\delta$, we get $k = \frac{ed-1}{\phi(N)} < \frac{ed}{\phi(N)} < d < N^\delta$. On the other hand, since $q < p < 2q$, then $p + q = O(N^{\frac{1}{2}})$. Using *inverse problem theorem* with $B = e$ and $\beta = \frac{1}{2}$, we can solve the equation $x(A + y) + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{e}$, with $|x| < X = N^\delta$ and $|y| = N^\beta$ provided that

$$\delta < 1 + \frac{1}{3}\beta - \frac{2}{3}\sqrt{\beta^2 + 3\beta} = \frac{7}{6} - \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{7} \approx 0.284.$$

Using $p + q = y$, we can get p and q easily. □

2.4 de Weger's Generalization of Wiener's Attack

In 2002, *de Weger* [48] proposed a generalization of Wiener's attack on RSA. *de Weger* extended Wiener's bound $\frac{\sqrt{6\sqrt{2}}}{6}N^{\frac{1}{4}}$ to $d < \frac{N^{\frac{3}{4}}}{|p-q|}$ which is equivalent with Wiener's bound for the standard RSA, that is for $|p-q| = O\left(N^{\frac{1}{2}}\right)$. We describe below the attack of *de Weger*.

Theorem 8. (*de Weger*) *Let $N = pq$ be an RSA modulus with $q < p < 2q$ and $p - q = N^\beta$. Let $e < \phi(N)$ be a public exponent and $d < N^\delta$ be the corresponding private key. If $\delta < \frac{3}{4} - \beta$, then, we can find the factorization of N in time polynomial in $\log N$.*

Proof. We transform the equation $ed - k(N + 1 - p - q) = 1$ to

$$ed - k(N + 1 - \sqrt{N}) = 1 - k(p + q - 2\sqrt{N}).$$

Dividing by $(N + 1 - 2\sqrt{N}d)$ and using $p + q > 2\sqrt{N}$, we get

$$\left| \frac{e}{N + 1 - 2\sqrt{N}} - \frac{k}{d} \right| = \frac{|1 - k(p + q - 2\sqrt{N})|}{(N + 1 - 2\sqrt{N}d)} < \frac{k(p + q - 2\sqrt{N})}{(N + 1 - 2\sqrt{N})}. \quad (2.3)$$

Consider the terms of the right side of (2.3). We have $N + 1 - 2\sqrt{N} > \frac{1}{2}N$ for $N \geq 12$. Using Lemma 1, We get

$$p + q - 2\sqrt{N} = \frac{(p + q)^2 - 4N}{p + q + 2\sqrt{N}} < \frac{(p - q)^2}{4\sqrt{N}}.$$

Since $e < \phi(N)$, then $k = \frac{ed-1}{\phi(N)} < \frac{ed}{\phi(N)} < d$. Consequently, the inequality (2.3) gives

$$\left| \frac{e}{N + 1 - 2\sqrt{N}} - \frac{k}{d} \right| < \frac{k}{d} \cdot \frac{\frac{(p-q)^2}{4\sqrt{N}}}{\frac{1}{2}N} < \frac{(p - q)^2}{2N\sqrt{N}}.$$

In order to apply Theorem 1, a sufficient condition is

$$\frac{(p - q)^2}{2N\sqrt{N}} < \frac{1}{2d^2},$$

or equivalently $d < \frac{N^{\frac{3}{4}}}{|p-q|}$. Using $d < N^\delta$ and $|p - q| = N^\beta$, the condition is fulfilled if $\delta < \frac{3}{4} - \beta$. Hence we can use the continued fraction expansion of $\frac{e}{N+1-2\sqrt{N}}$ to find $\frac{k}{d}$ among the convergence. \square

Lattice-Reduction Cryptanalysis of RSA

A number of lattice attacks on RSA Cryptosystem are motivated by the LLL algorithm and Coppersmith's techniques for solving polynomial equations. In this section we consider some attacks on RSA that are related to lattice methods and the references therein for detailed information.

Factoring the RSA Modulus with Partial Knowledge of p

Theorem 9. *Let $N = pq$ be an RSA modulus with $p > q$. Furthermore, let k be an (unknown) integer that is not a multiple of q . Suppose we know an approximation \tilde{p} of kp such that $|kp - \tilde{p}| < N^{\frac{1}{4}}$. Then we can find the factorization of N in time polynomial in $\log N$.*

Proof. Write $x_0 = kp - \tilde{p}$ and $f_p(x) = \tilde{p} + x$. Then $f_p(x_0) = kp \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ with $p > N^{\frac{1}{2}}$. We can then apply Coppersmith's theorem with $d = 1$, $\beta = \frac{1}{2}$ and $c_N = 1$ and get the root x_0 since $|x_0| < N^{\frac{1}{4}}$. Hence $kp = x_0 + \tilde{p}$ and $\gcd(kp, N) = p$ since $k \not\equiv 0 \pmod{q}$. \square

2.5 Blömer and May's Class of Weak Keys

We consider the class of public keys (N, e) satisfying an equation $ex - y\phi(N) = z$. In 2004, Blömer and May [4] showed that using such exponents makes RSA insecure if $N = pq$ with $p - q = cN^{\frac{1}{2}}$ for some constant $0 < c \leq 1$ and

$$0 \leq x < \frac{1}{3} \sqrt{\frac{\phi(N)}{e} \frac{N^{\frac{1}{4}}}{p - q}}$$

and

$$|z| \leq \frac{p - q}{\phi(N)N^{\frac{1}{4}}} ex.$$

We reformulate this attack in the following result where the primes p and q can be unbalanced.

Theorem 10. *Let (N, e) be an RSA public key tuple with $N = pq$ and $q < p$. Suppose that e satisfies an equation $ex - y\phi(N) = z$ with $\gcd(x, y) = 1$ and*

$$xy < \frac{N}{4(p+q)} \text{ and } |z| < \frac{(p-q)N^{\frac{1}{4}}y}{3(p+q)}.$$

Then N can be factored in polynomial time.

Proof. Rewrite $ex - y\phi(N) = z$ as $ex - yN = z - k(p + q - 1)$. Then

$$\left| \frac{e}{N} - \frac{y}{x} \right| = \frac{|z - k(p + q - 1)|}{Nx} \leq \frac{|z| + k(p + q - 1)}{Nx}. \quad (2.4)$$

Suppose $\gcd(x, y) = 1$ and $|z| < \frac{(p-q)N^{\frac{1}{4}}y}{3(p+q)}$ then $|z| < N^{\frac{1}{4}}y$. Hence

$$|z| + (p + q + 1)y \leq N^{\frac{1}{4}}y + (p + q + 1)y = (N^{\frac{1}{4}} + p + q + 1)y < 2(p + q)y.$$

Plugging in (2.4), We get

$$\left| \frac{e}{N} - \frac{y}{x} \right| < \frac{2(p + q)y}{Nx}.$$

Now, assume that $xy < \frac{N}{4(p+q)}$. Then $\frac{2(p+q)y}{Nx} < \frac{1}{2x^2}$ which implies

$$\left| \frac{e}{N} - \frac{y}{x} \right| < \frac{1}{2x^2}.$$

Then $\frac{y}{x}$ is a convergent of the continued fraction of $\frac{e}{N}$. Using x and y , define

$$U = N + 1 - \frac{ex}{y}, \quad V = \sqrt{|U^2 - 4N|}.$$

Transforming the equation $ex - (p-1)(q-1)y = z$ into $p + q - \left(N + 1 - \frac{ex}{y}\right) = \frac{z}{y}$, we get

$$|p + q - U| = \left| p + q - \left(N + 1 - \frac{ex}{y} \right) \right| = \frac{|z|}{y} < \frac{(p-q)N^{\frac{1}{4}}}{3(p+q)} < N^{\frac{1}{4}}. \quad (2.5)$$

Now we have

$$\begin{aligned} |(p-q)^2 - V^2| &= |(p-q)^2 - |U^2 - 4N|| \\ &\leq |(p-q)^2 - U^2 + 4N| \\ &= |(p+q)^2 - U^2|. \end{aligned}$$

Dividing by $p - q + V$, we get

$$|p - q - V| \leq \frac{|(p+q)^2 - U^2|}{p - q + V} = \frac{|p + q - U|(p + q + U)}{p - q + V}. \quad (2.6)$$

Observe that (2.5) implies $p + q + U < 2(p+q) + N^{\frac{1}{4}} < 3(p+q)$. On the other hand, we have $p - q + V > p - q$. Plugging in (2.6), we get

$$|p - q - V| < \frac{3(p+q)(p-q)N^{\frac{1}{4}}}{3(p+q)(p-q)} = N^{\frac{1}{4}}.$$

Combing this with (2.5), we deduce

$$\left| p - \frac{U+V}{2} \right| = \left| \frac{p+q}{2} - \frac{U}{2} + \frac{p-q}{2} - \frac{V}{2} \right| \leq \left| \frac{p+q}{2} - \frac{U}{2} \right| + \left| \frac{p-q}{2} - \frac{V}{2} \right| < N^{\frac{1}{4}}.$$

Hence $\frac{U+V}{2}$ is an approximation of p up to an error term of at most $N^{\frac{1}{4}}$. Then *Coppersmith's theorem* will find p in polynomial time. \square

2.6 Attack based on $\psi(N)$ - Constrained Keys

The starting point of the former attacks is the defining equation $ed \equiv 1 \pmod{\phi(N)}$, which means that there exists an integer k such that $ed - k\phi(N) = 1$. The main results of these attacks are based on the arithmetical properties encoded in the public exponent e and the Euler totient function $\phi(N)$. Such keys (N, e) are called weak keys in [4] and $\phi(N)$ -constrained keys in [36]. Instead of focusing on the information encoded in the public exponent e relatively to $\phi(N)$, an alternative way proposed in [36] is to replace $\phi(N)$ by any function F with special properties. In that, an attack was proposed on the public exponents e satisfying $eY - p(q-u)X = Z$, with suitably small unknown integers u, X, Y, Z . It is shown that every public exponent with these properties yields the factorization of N in polynomial time and that the number of such keys is at least $O\left(N^{\frac{3}{4}} - \epsilon\right)$. In this work we consider the class of the public exponents e satisfying the diophantine equation.

$$(e + u)X^m - \psi(N)Y^m = Z, \quad (2.7)$$

where m is an integer satisfying $1 \leq m \leq \frac{\log N}{\log 32}$ and $\psi(N) = (p+1)(q-1)$. For notational convenience, we define $\alpha \in R$ so that $\psi(N) = N^{1-\alpha}$. Typically, $\psi(N) \approx N$ and therefore $\alpha \approx 0$. We present a new method that finds p and q in polynomial time for every exponent e satisfying (2.7) with

$$Y \leq \left(\frac{me^{1-\frac{1}{m}}N^{\frac{1}{m}-\frac{1}{4}}\psi(N)}{2\left(\sqrt{3}N^{\frac{1}{4}}e + 2\psi(N)\right)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$|Z| \leq \min\left\{N^{\frac{1}{4}}X^m, \frac{\sqrt{3}N^{\frac{1}{4}}e + 2\psi(N)}{2^m N^{\frac{1}{m}-\frac{1}{4}}\psi(N)^{1-\frac{1}{m}}}\right\} Y^m$$

$$0 \leq u \leq \frac{N^{\frac{1}{4}}X^m}{Y^m}.$$

In particular, we show that our attack works for all public exponents e with the special structure $e = \lfloor \psi(N) \frac{X^m}{Y^m} \rfloor + 1$ where X, Y are relatively prime integers satisfying

$$N^{-\frac{1}{4m}} Y \leq X \leq Y < \frac{\sqrt{2m}}{4} N^{\frac{1}{4} + \frac{\alpha}{2m} - \frac{\alpha}{2}}.$$

Moreover, we show that the number of such exponents is at least $O\left(mN^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{\alpha}{m} - \alpha - \epsilon}\right)$ and should not be used in the design of an RSA Cryptosystem. As in [4] and [7], our attack will be based on combining the theory of continued fractions and Coppersmiths technique.

Similarly to *Wiener's* attack, our approach is also based on the continued fraction algorithm. More precisely, we will use the following classical theorem on diophantine approximations .

Properties of basic lemmas

Let $N = pq$ be an RSA modulus where p and q are primes of equal bitsize. We begin with the following useful lemma.

Lemma 2. *Let $N = pq$ be an RSA modulus with $q < p < 2q$. Then*

$$N - 1 - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} \sqrt{N} < \psi(N) < N - 1.$$

Proof. Since $q < p < 2q$, then $q^2 < N < 2q^2$. This gives

$$\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} \sqrt{N} < q < \sqrt{N}. \quad (2.8)$$

On the other hand, since $p = \frac{N}{q}$, then(2.8) gives

$$\sqrt{N} < p < \sqrt{2}\sqrt{N}. \quad (2.9)$$

Combining (2.8) and (2.9), we get

$$0 < p - q < \sqrt{2}\sqrt{N} - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} \sqrt{N} = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} \sqrt{2}.$$

Rewriting $\psi(N) = (p+1)(q-1) = N-1 - (p-q)$, we get

$$N-1 - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}\sqrt{N} < N-1 - (p-q) < N-1,$$

□

Notice that for prime difference $p-q \leq N^{\frac{1}{4}}$ an algorithm of Fermat finds the factorisation of N in polynomial time (see [48]).

Lemma 3. *Let $N = pq > 39$ with $q < p < 2q$. Let m be an integer with $1 \leq m \leq \frac{\log N}{\log 32}$. Then*

$$\frac{1}{mN^{1-\frac{1}{m}}} < N^{\frac{1}{m}} - \psi(N)^{\frac{1}{m}} < \frac{\sqrt{3}\sqrt{N}}{2m\psi(N)^{1-\frac{1}{m}}}.$$

Proof. Note that

$$N - \psi(N) = \left(N^{\frac{1}{m}} - \psi(N)^{\frac{1}{m}}\right) \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} N^{\frac{m-1-i}{m}} \psi(N)^{\frac{i}{m}},$$

and

$$N^{\frac{1}{m}} - \psi(N)^{\frac{1}{m}} = \frac{N - \psi(N)}{\sum_{i=0}^{m-1} N^{\frac{m-1-i}{m}} \psi(N)^{\frac{i}{m}}}. \quad (2.10)$$

First, consider the denominator of (2.10). Since $\psi(N) < N$, then

$$\sum_{i=0}^{m-1} \psi(N)^{\frac{m-1-i}{m}} \psi(N)^{\frac{i}{m}} < \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} N^{\frac{m-1-i}{m}} \psi(N)^{\frac{i}{m}} < \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} N^{\frac{m-1-i}{m}} N^{\frac{i}{m}}$$

that is

$$m\psi(N)^{\frac{1-\frac{1}{m}}{m}} \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} \psi(N)^{\frac{i}{m}} < mN^{1-\frac{1}{m}}. \quad (2.11)$$

Next, consider the numerator of (2.10). By Lemma 2, we have $N-1 - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}\sqrt{N} < \psi N < N-1$. This gives for $N > 39$

$$1 < N - \psi N < 1 + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}\sqrt{N} \leq \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}\sqrt{N}.$$

Combining this with (2.11) in (2.10), we get

$$\frac{1}{mN^{1-\frac{1}{m}}} < N^{\frac{1}{m}} - \psi N^{\frac{1}{m}} < \frac{\sqrt{3}\sqrt{N}}{2m\psi N^{1-\frac{1}{m}}}.$$

□

The following lemma gives an estimation involving $\psi N^{\frac{1}{m}}$ and N .

Lemma 4. *Let $N = pq > 30$ with $q < p < 2q$. Let m be an integer with $1 \leq m \leq \frac{\log N}{\log 32}$. Then*

$$(2 + \sqrt{3}) \psi N^{\frac{1}{m}} > 2^m N^{\frac{1}{m} - \frac{1}{4}}.$$

Proof. Using Lemma 2, we get

$$\psi N^{\frac{1}{m}} > \left(N - 1 - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} \sqrt{N} \right)^{\frac{1}{m}}.$$

Define ϵ by

$$N - 1 - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} \sqrt{N} = N^{1-\epsilon}.$$

Then for $N > 30$ we have $\epsilon < \frac{1}{20}$. It follows that for all $m \geq 1$

$$\left(N - 1 - \frac{\sqrt{2}\sqrt{N}}{2} \right)^{\frac{1}{m}} = N^{\frac{1}{m} - \frac{\epsilon}{m}} \geq N^{\frac{1}{m} - \epsilon} > N^{\frac{1}{m} - \frac{1}{20}} = N^{\frac{1}{m} - \frac{1}{4}} N^{\frac{1}{5}}.$$

Since $m < \frac{\log N}{\log 32}$, then $(2 + \sqrt{3}) N^{\frac{1}{5}} > N^{\frac{1}{5}} > 2^m$

$$(2 + \sqrt{3}) N^{\frac{1}{m} - \frac{1}{4}} N^{\frac{1}{5}} > 2^m N^{\frac{1}{m} - \frac{1}{4}} N^{\frac{1}{5}} > 2^m N^{\frac{1}{m} - \frac{1}{4}},$$

and finally

$$(2 + \sqrt{3}) \psi N^{\frac{1}{m}} > 2^m N^{\frac{1}{m} - \frac{1}{4}}$$

□

Let e be a public exponent and u a positive integer with $u < N^{\frac{1}{4}}$. The following lemma states the error terms in the approximation of $(e + u)^{\frac{1}{m}}$ by $e^{\frac{1}{m}}$.

Lemma 5. *Let $N = pq$ with $q < p < 2q$. Let m be an integer with $1 \leq m \leq \frac{\log N}{\log 32}$ $0 \leq u \leq N^{\frac{1}{4}}$, then*

$$(e + u)^{\frac{1}{m}} - e^{\frac{1}{m}} \leq \frac{N^{\frac{1}{4}}}{me^{1-\frac{1}{m}}}.$$

Proof. Put $x = (e + u)^{\frac{1}{m}}$ and $y = e^{\frac{1}{m}}$. Since $u \geq 0$, then $x \geq y$ and

$$u = x^m - y^m = (x - y) \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} x^{m-1-i} y^i \geq (x - y) \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} y^{m-1-i} y^i = m(x - y)y^{m-1}.$$

This gives

$$x - y \leq \frac{u}{my^{m-1}}.$$

Assume that $u \leq N^{\frac{1}{4}}$. Then

$$(e + u)^{\frac{1}{m}} - e^{\frac{1}{m}} = x - y \leq \frac{u}{my^{m-1}} \leq \frac{N^{\frac{1}{4}}}{me^{1-\frac{1}{m}}}.$$

□

Let us focus on the Diophantine equation (2.7). The following lemma proves the existence of a link between the small solutions of this equation and the approximations of $\left(\frac{e}{\psi(N)}\right)^{\frac{1}{m}}$

Lemma 6. *Let $N = pq$ with $q < p < 2q$. Let e be a public exponent and X, Y be relatively prime positive integers. Put $eY^m - \psi(N)X^m = Z$. Then*

$$\left| \frac{X}{Y} - \left(\frac{e}{\psi(N)}\right)^{\frac{1}{m}} \right| \leq \frac{2^{m-1}|Z|}{me^{1-\frac{1}{m}}\psi(N)^{\frac{1}{m}}Y^m}.$$

Proof. Let $\delta = \left(\frac{e}{\psi(N)}\right)^{\frac{1}{m}}$ and $\theta_k = \delta \exp\left(\frac{2k\pi i}{m}\right)$ for $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, m-1$ we have

$$|\psi(N)X^m - eY^m| = \psi(N) \prod_{k=0}^{m-1} |X - \theta_k Y| = \psi(N) |X - \delta Y| \prod_{k=1}^{m-1} |X - \theta_k Y|.$$

Hence

$$|Z| = \psi(N)|X - \delta Y| \prod_{k=1}^{m-1} |X - \theta_k Y|. \quad (2.12)$$

Since $X > 0$, $Y > 0$ and $\delta > 0$, then $|X - \theta_k Y| \geq |X - \delta Y|$. Hence for $k \geq 1$,

$$|X - \theta_k Y| \geq \frac{1}{2} (|X - \theta_k Y| + |X - \delta Y|) \geq \frac{1}{2} |\delta - \theta_k| Y.$$

This gives

$$\prod_{k=1}^{m-1} |X - \theta_k Y| \geq \frac{Y^{m-1}}{2^{m-1}} \prod_{k=1}^{m-1} |\delta - \theta_k|. \quad (2.13)$$

Further, let $g(x) = \psi(N)x^m - e$. Then

$$\prod_{k=0}^{m-1} |x - \theta_k| = \frac{|g(x)|}{\psi(N)}$$

and

$$\prod_{k=1}^{m-1} |\delta - \theta_k| = \frac{|g'(\delta)|}{\psi(N)} = m\delta^{m-1}.$$

Combining this with (2.13), we get

$$\prod_{k=1}^{m-1} |X - \theta_k Y| \geq \frac{m\delta^{m-1} Y^{m-1}}{2^{m-1}}.$$

Using this inequality in (2.12), we get

$$|Z| \geq \psi(N)|X - \delta Y| \frac{m\delta^{m-1} Y^{m-1}}{2^{m-1}}$$

and finally

$$\left| \frac{X}{Y} - \delta \right| \leq \frac{2^{m-1} |Z|}{m\delta^{m-1} \psi(N) Y^m}.$$

Replacing $\delta = \left(\frac{\epsilon}{\psi(N)} \right)^{\frac{1}{m}}$.

□

Lemma 7. Let $N = pq$ with $q < p < 2q$. Let $T > 0$ and $S = \sqrt{T^2 + 4n}$. Then

$$|S - (p + q)| < |T - (p - q)|.$$

Proof. Using the identity $(p + q)^2 - 4n = (p - q)^2$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} |S - (p + q)| &= \frac{|S^2 - (p + q)^2|}{S + p + q} \\ &= \frac{|T^2 + 4n - (p + q)^2|}{S + p + q} \\ &= \frac{|T^2 - (p - q)^2|}{S + p + q} \\ &= \frac{|T^2 - (p - q)| (T + p - q)}{S + p + q}. \end{aligned}$$

Since $T < S$ and $p - q < p + q$, then $T + p - q < S + p + q$. This gives

$$|S - (p + q)| < |T - (p - q)|.$$

□

The attack algorithm

We present the attack on the public exponents e verifying (1) that we have considered. Both *continued fraction* and *Coppersmith's method* techniques will be applied. We begin by linking the small solutions of the diophantine equation (2.7) to the diophantine approximations of $\left(\frac{e+u}{N}\right)^{\frac{1}{m}}$ for any positive integer u with $u \leq N^{\frac{1}{4}}$

Theorem 11. *Let $N = pq$ with $q < p < 2q$. Let e be a public key and $m \geq 1$ be an integer. Suppose that e satisfies the equation $eY^m - \psi(N)X^m = Z$ with*

$$|Z| \leq \frac{\sqrt{3}N^{\frac{1}{4}}e + 2\psi(N)}{2^m N^{\frac{1}{m} - \frac{1}{4}} \psi(N)^{1 - \frac{1}{m}}} Y^m \quad (2.14)$$

and

$$|Y| \leq \left(\frac{me^{1 - \frac{1}{m}} N^{\frac{1}{m} - \frac{1}{4}} \psi(N)}{2 \left(\sqrt{3}N^{\frac{1}{4}}e + 2\psi(N) \right)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}. \quad (2.15)$$

Then for all positive integers $u \leq N^{\frac{1}{4}}$, $\frac{X}{Y}$ is a convergent of $\left(\frac{e+u}{N}\right)^{\frac{1}{m}}$.

Proof. We have

$$\left| \frac{(e+u)^{\frac{1}{m}}}{N^{\frac{1}{m}}} - \frac{X}{Y} \right| \leq \left| \frac{(e+u)^{\frac{1}{m}}}{N^{\frac{1}{m}}} - \frac{e^{\frac{1}{m}}}{N^{\frac{1}{m}}} \right| + \left| \frac{(e)^{\frac{1}{m}}}{\psi(N)^{\frac{1}{m}}} - \frac{e^{\frac{1}{m}}}{N^{\frac{1}{m}}} \right| + \left| \frac{(e)^{\frac{1}{m}}}{\psi(N)^{\frac{1}{m}}} - \frac{X}{Y} \right|. \quad (2.16)$$

Using Lemma 5, we get

$$\left| \frac{(e+u)^{\frac{1}{m}}}{N^{\frac{1}{m}}} - \frac{e^{\frac{1}{m}}}{N^{\frac{1}{m}}} \right| = \frac{|(e+u)^{\frac{1}{m}} - e^{\frac{1}{m}}|}{N^{\frac{1}{m}}} \leq \frac{N^{\frac{1}{4}-\frac{1}{m}}}{me^{1-\frac{1}{m}}}. \quad (2.17)$$

On the other hand, applying Lemma 3, we get

$$\left| \frac{(e+u)^{\frac{1}{m}}}{\psi(N)^{\frac{1}{m}}} - \frac{e^{\frac{1}{m}}}{N^{\frac{1}{m}}} \right| = \frac{e^{\frac{1}{m}} |N^{\frac{1}{m}} - \psi(N)^{\frac{1}{m}}|}{\psi(N)^{\frac{1}{m}} N^{\frac{1}{m}}} < \frac{\sqrt{3}N^{\frac{1}{2}-\frac{1}{m}}e^{\frac{1}{m}}}{2m\psi(N)}. \quad (2.18)$$

Finally, by Lemma 6, we have

$$\left| \frac{(e+u)^{\frac{1}{m}}}{\psi(N)^{\frac{1}{m}}} - \frac{X}{Y} \right| \leq \frac{2^{m-1}|Z|}{me^{1-\frac{1}{m}}\psi(N)^{\frac{1}{m}}Y^m}. \quad (2.19)$$

Combining (2.17),(2.18) and (2.19) in (2.16), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \frac{(e+u)^{\frac{1}{m}}}{N^{\frac{1}{m}}} - \frac{X}{Y} \right| &< \frac{N^{\frac{1}{4}-\frac{1}{m}}}{me^{1-\frac{1}{m}}} + \frac{\sqrt{3}N^{\frac{1}{2}-\frac{1}{m}}e^{\frac{1}{m}}}{2m\psi(N)} + \frac{2^{m-1}|Z|}{me^{1-\frac{1}{m}}\psi(N)^{\frac{1}{m}}Y^m} \\ &= \frac{\sqrt{3}N^{\frac{1}{4}}e + 2\psi(N)}{me^{1-\frac{1}{m}}N^{\frac{1}{m}-\frac{1}{4}}\psi(N)} + \frac{2^{m-1}|Z|}{me^{1-\frac{1}{m}}\psi(N)^{\frac{1}{m}}Y^m}. \end{aligned}$$

Assume that Z satisfies (2.14). Then

$$\left| \frac{(e+u)^{\frac{1}{m}}}{N^{\frac{1}{m}}} - \frac{X}{Y} \right| < \frac{\sqrt{3}N^{\frac{1}{4}}e + 2\psi(N)}{me^{1-\frac{1}{m}}N^{\frac{1}{m}-\frac{1}{4}}\psi(N)}.$$

Similarly, assume that Y satisfies (2.15). Then

$$\left| \frac{(e+u)^{\frac{1}{m}}}{N^{\frac{1}{m}}} - \frac{X}{Y} \right| < \frac{1}{2Y^2}$$

which means, by theorem 1, that $\frac{X}{Y}$ is a convergent of $\left(\frac{e+u}{N}\right)^{\frac{1}{m}}$. \square

The next theorem ensures that the modulus N can be factored if e has a more special structure.

Theorem 12. *Let $N = pq$ with $q < p < 2q$. Let e be a public exponent. Let m, X, Y be a positive integers. if $eY^m - \psi(N)X^m = Z$ with $|Z| < 2N^{\frac{1}{4}}X^m$, then N can be factored in polynomial time.*

Proof. From $eY^m - \psi(N)X^m = Z$ with $\psi(N) = (p+1)(q-1) = N-1-(p-q)$, we get

$$p - q = N - 1 - \frac{eY^m}{X^m} + \frac{Z}{X^m}.$$

Let $T = |N - 1 - \frac{eY^m}{X^m}|$ and suppose that $|Z| < 2N^{\frac{1}{4}}X^m$. We have

$$|T - (p - q)| \leq \left| \frac{Z}{X^m} \right| = \frac{|Z|}{X^m} \leq 2N^{\frac{1}{4}}.$$

This means that T is an approximation of $p - q$ with an error term less than $2N^{\frac{1}{4}}$.

Next put $S = \sqrt{T^2 + 4N}$ and $P = \frac{S+T}{2}$ Applying Lemma 7, we get

$$|S - (p + q)| < |T - (p - q)| < 2N^{\frac{1}{4}}.$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} |P - p| &= \frac{1}{2}|S + T - 2p| \\ &= \frac{1}{2}|S - (p + q) + (T - (p - q))| \\ &= \frac{1}{2}|S - (p + q)| + \frac{1}{2}|T - (p - q)| \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2}|S - (p + q)| + \frac{1}{2}|T - (p - q)| \\ &< N^{\frac{1}{4}}. \end{aligned}$$

It follows that P is an approximation of p upto an error term bounded by $2N^{\frac{1}{4}}$. We can then apply Theorem 4 to find p and the factorization of N .

Let us briefly summarize the new attack. Recall that the input is a public exponent e such that $(e + u)Y^m - \psi(N)X^m = Z$ with unknown integers X, Y, Z, u satisfying $0 \leq u \leq N^{\frac{1}{4}}$, $|Z| < N^{\frac{1}{4}}X^m$ and the inequalities (2.14),(2.15). Notice that, since $0 < e < N$, the right hand side of (2.15) satisfies.

$$\left(\frac{me^{1-\frac{1}{4}}N^{\frac{1}{m}-\frac{1}{4}}\psi(N)}{2\left(\sqrt{3}N^{\frac{1}{4}}e + 2\psi(N)\right)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \leq \left(\frac{mN^{1-\frac{1}{m}}N^{\frac{1}{m}-\frac{1}{4}}\psi(N)}{4\psi(N)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} = \left(\frac{mN^{\frac{3}{4}}}{4} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{\sqrt{m}N^{\frac{3}{8}}}{2}.$$

INPUT : The Public Key modulus (N, e) satisfying $N = pq$.

OUTPUT: The prime factor p .

1. $m = 1$.

2. Compute $Y_0(m) = \frac{\sqrt{m}N^{\frac{3}{8}}}{2}$.

3. Compute the continued fraction expansion of $\left(\frac{e}{N}\right)^{\frac{1}{m}}$.

4. For every convergent $\frac{X}{Y}$ with $Y < Y_0$.

i. Compute $T = |N - 1 - \frac{eY^m}{X^m}|, S = \sqrt{T^2 + 4N}, \tilde{P} = \frac{S+T}{2}$.

ii. Apply Coppersmith's algorithm to \tilde{P} . If the prime factor p is found, then stop.

5. $m = m + 1$. Return to Step 2 if $m \leq \frac{\log N}{\log 32}$.

Table 3 : Algorithm 2

□

Chapter 3

RSA with modulus $N = p^2q$

We present new cryptanalysis on the modulus of $N = p^2q$ by using continued fractions method as the first analysis motivated from some previous attacks. We consider the public value, e satisfying the following generalized key equation,

$$eX - NY = (p^2u + q^2v)Z$$

such that u is an integer multiple of 2 and v is an integer multiple of 3. If

$$\gcd(X, Y) = 1, |p^2u - q^2v| < N^{1/2}, X|Z| < \frac{N}{2|p^2u + q^2v|}$$

then N can be factored in polynomial time using continued fractions. We also show that the number of such parameters e satisfying the equation are at least $N^{\frac{1}{3}-\epsilon}$ where $\epsilon > 0$ is arbitrarily small for large N .

In the second attack, we focus on k instances of (N_i, e_i) where $N_i = p_i^2q_i$ together with its generalized system of key equations $e_ix - N_iy_i = (p_i^2u + q_i^2v)z_i$. We prove that, each RSA moduli N_i can be factored in polynomial time if $x < N^\delta, y_i < N^\delta, |z_i| < \frac{\sqrt{2}N^{1/2}}{|p_i^2u - q_i^2v|}$ where $\delta = \frac{k}{3} - \alpha k, N = \min_i N_i$. Finally, for the third attack, we prove that we are able to factor k RSA moduli of the form $N_i = p_i^2q_i$ when k instance

of (N_i, e_i) are available and the variables (x_i, y, z_i, δ) in the generalized system of key equations given by $e_i x_i - N_i y = (p_i^2 u + q_i^2 v) z_i$ satisfying $x_i < N^\delta, y < N^\delta, |z_i| < \frac{\sqrt{2} N^{1/2}}{|p_i^2 u - q_i^2 v|}$ where $\delta = \beta s - \alpha s - \frac{2s}{3}$, with $N = \max_i N_i$ and $\min_i e_i = N^\beta$.

For the second and third attack, we transform the equations into a simultaneous diophantine problem and applying lattice basis reduction techniques to find parameters (x, y_i) or (y, x_i) . This leads to a suitable approximation of $p^2 u + q^2 v$ which allow us to apply the theorem that we propose in first cryptanalysis to compute the prime factor p_i and q_i of the *moduli* N_i . We also prove that the propose attacks enables to factor the k RSA *moduli* N_i simultaneously.

We give brief review on continued fractions expansion, lattice basic reduction and simultaneous diophantine approximation that will be used.

Theorem 13 (29). *Let L be a lattice of dimension ω with a basis v_1, \dots, v_ω . The LLL algorithm produces a reduced basis b_1, \dots, b_ω satisfying*

$$\|b_1\| \leq \|b_2\| \leq \dots \leq \|b_i\| \leq 2^{\frac{\omega(\omega-1)}{4(\omega+1-i)}} \det(L)^{\frac{1}{\omega+1-i}},$$

for all $1 \leq i \leq \omega$.

One of the important application of the LLL algorithm is it provides a solution to the simultaneous Diophantine approximations problem which is defined as follows. Let $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n$ be n real numbers and ϵ a real number such that $0 < \epsilon < 1$. A classical theorem of Dirichlet asserts that there exist integers p_1, \dots, p_n and a positive integer $q \leq \epsilon^{-n}$ such that $|q\alpha_i - p_i| < \epsilon$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$.

In [29] described a method to find simultaneous diophantine approximations to rational numbers which they consider a lattice with real entries. Hence, we state here a similar result for a lattice with integer entries.

Theorem 14. [29] (*Simultaneous Diophantine Approximations*). *There is a polynomial time algorithm, for given rational numbers $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n$ and $0 < \epsilon < 1$, to compute integers p_1, \dots, p_n and a positive integer q such that $\max_i |q\alpha_i - p_i| < \epsilon$ and $q \leq 2^{n(n-3)/4} 3^n \epsilon^{-n}$.*

3.1 The First Attack on modulus $N = p^2q$

We present our first attack on RSA with the modulus $N = p^2q$. The following lemma shows that any approximation of $p^2u + q^2v$ will lead to an approximation of q . We begin with a lemma fixing the size of prime factor p and q of RSA-type modulus $N = p^2q$.

Lemma 8. *Let $N = p^2q$ with $q < p < 2q$. Then $2^{-1/3}N^{1/3} < q < N^{1/3} < p < 2^{1/3}N^{1/3}$.*

Proof. Suppose $q < p < 2q$. Multiplying by p^2 , we get $N < p^3 < 2N$. Hence $N^{1/3} < p < \frac{21}{3}N^{1/3}$. Multiplying $q < p < 2q$ by pq and q^2 , we get $q^3 < pq^2 < 2q^3$ and $pq^2 < N < 2pq^2$, respectively. This implies $2^{-2/3}N^{1/3} < q < N^{1/3}$. \square

Lemma 9. *Let $N = p^2q$ with $q < p < 2q$. Let $u, v \in \mathbb{N}$ such that u is an integer multiple of 2 and v is an integer multiple of 3. Let $|p^2u - q^2v| < N^{1/2}$. Set $S = (p^2u + q^2v)Z$, where $1 \leq |Z| < p^{\frac{\sqrt{2}N^{1/2}}{|p^2u - q^2v|}}$, then $uvZ^2q = \lfloor \frac{S^2}{4N} \rfloor$.*

Proof. First, we consider $S = (p^2u + q^2v)Z$. Then, observe that

$$\begin{aligned}
S^2 &= ((p^2u + q^2v)Z)^2 \\
&= (p^2Zu + q^2Zv)^2 \\
&= (p^2Zu + q^2Zv)(p^2Zu + q^2Zv) \\
&= (p^2Zu)^2 + 2(p^2Zu)(q^2Zv) + (q^2Zv)^2 \\
&= (p^2Zu - q^2Zv)^2 + 4(p^2q^2uvZ^2) \\
&= (p^2Zu - q^2Zv)^2 + 4NquvZ^2.
\end{aligned}$$

We obtain

$$S^2 - 4NquvZ^2 = (p^2Zu - q^2Zv)^2 > 0. \quad (3.1)$$

Hence, we obtain (3.1) by $4N$ and we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\left| \frac{S^2}{4N} - uvZ^2q \right| &= \left| \frac{S^2 - 4NquvZ^2}{4N} \right| \\
&= \frac{(p^2Zu - q^2Zv)^2}{4N} \\
&= \frac{(p^2u - q^2v)^2 Z^2}{4N} \\
&< \frac{(p^2u - q^2v)^2 (\frac{\sqrt{2}N^{1/2}}{|p^2u - q^2v|})^2}{4N} \\
&< \frac{(\sqrt{2}N^{1/2})^2}{4N} = \frac{1}{2}.
\end{aligned}$$

Which we deduce $uvZ^2q = \lfloor \frac{S^2}{4N} \rfloor$. □

Lemma 10. *Let $N = p^2q$ with $q < p < 2q$. Let e be an exponent satisfying an equation $eX - NY = (p^2u + q^2v)Z$ for some $u, v \in \mathbb{N}$ and with $\gcd(X, Y) = 1$ and $X|Z| < \frac{N}{2|p^2u + q^2v|}$ then $\frac{X}{Y}$ is a convergent of the continued fraction $\frac{e}{N}$.*

Proof. Suppose that $X|Z| < \frac{N}{2|p^2u + q^2v|}$ satisfying with the equation $eX - NY =$

$(p^2u + q^2v)Z$ and if we divide by NX , then we obtain

$$\left| \frac{e}{N} - \frac{Y}{X} \right| = \left| \frac{(p^2u + q^2v)Z}{NX} \right|.$$

In order to apply Legendres theorem, observe that, if $X|Z| < \frac{N}{2|p^2u+q^2v|}$, then $\frac{|(p^2u+q^2v)Z|}{NX} < \frac{1}{2X^2}$ is satisfied. Hence, we conclude that $\frac{Y}{X}$ is convergent of continued fraction $\frac{e}{N}$. \square

The following theorem shows that how to factor $N = p^2q$ completely.

Theorem 15. *Let $N = p^2q$ with $q < p < 2q$. Let $u, v \in \mathbb{N}$ such that u is an integer multiple of 2 and v is an integer multiple of 3. Let $|p^2u - q^2v| < N^{1/2}$. Let e be an exponent satisfying an equation $eX - NY = (p^2u + q^2v)Z$ with $\gcd(X, Y) = 1$. If $X|Z| < \frac{N}{2|p^2u+q^2v|}$ then N can be factored in polynomial time.*

Proof. Suppose that e be an exponent satisfying an equation $eX - NY = (p^2u + q^2v)Z$ with $\gcd(X, Y) = 1$. Let X and $|Z|$ satisfy the condition in Lemma 9, then $\frac{Y}{X}$ is convergent of continued fraction $\frac{e}{N}$. From the value of X and Y , we define $S = eX - NY$. Then from Lemma 9, this implies that $uvZ^2q = \left[\frac{S^2}{4N} \right]$.

It follows that we obtain $q = \gcd\left(\left[\frac{S^2}{4N} \right], N\right)$. \square

Now, we proposed the following algorithm for further recovering prime factorization of RSA-type module $N = p^2q$.

<p>INPUT : The Public Key modulus (N, e) satisfying $N = p^2q$.</p> <p>OUTPUT: The prime factors p and q.</p>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Compute the continued fraction $\frac{e}{N}$. 2. For each convergent $\frac{Y}{X}$ of $\frac{e}{N}$, compute $S = eX - NY$. 3. Compute $\left[\frac{S^2}{4N}\right]$. 4. Compute $q = \gcd\left(\left[\frac{S^2}{4N}\right], N\right)$ 5. If $1 < q < N$, then $p = \sqrt{\frac{N}{q}}$.

Table 4 : Algorithm 3

Example 1. As an illustration of our first attack, let N and e be as follows.

$$N = 64846371051769$$

$$e = 54715049302680.$$

Suppose that N and e satisfy all the conditions stated in Theorem 15. Then, we compute the continued fraction of $\frac{e}{N}$. The list of the convergent of continued fraction are shown as follows

$$\left[0, 1, \frac{5}{6}, \frac{11}{13}, \frac{27}{32}, \frac{1847}{2189}, \frac{11109}{13166}, \frac{12956}{15355}, \frac{37021}{43876}, \dots\right].$$

We may omit the first and the second entry. We start the convergent $\frac{5}{6}$ and we obtain

$$S = eX - NY = 4058440557235$$

and

$$\left[\frac{S^2}{4N}\right] = 63499851608.$$

Hence, if we compute $\gcd(63499851608, 64846371051769)=1$. Then, we try for next convergent $\frac{11}{13}$, we obtain

$$S = eX - NY = -2014440634619$$

and

$$\left[\frac{S^2}{4N} \right] = 15644557299.$$

Then, if we compute $\gcd(15644557299, 64846371051769)=1$. We proceed with the next convergent which is $\frac{27}{32}$ and we get

$$S = eX - NY = 29559287997$$

and

$$\left[\frac{S^2}{4N} \right] = 3368544.$$

Thus, we compute $\gcd(3368544, 64846371051769)=35089$ which leads to the factorization of N , since $q=35089$ and $p = \sqrt{\frac{N}{q}} = 42989$. Now, we give an estimation of the number of the exponents e satisfying the equation $eX - NY = (p^2u + q^2v)Z$. We begin by showing the following result. Suppose that u is an integer multiple of 2 and v is an integer multiple of 3 and the public parameter $e < N$ satisfies at most one equation $eX - NY = (p^2u + q^2v)Z$ where the parameters X, Y and Z satisfy the condition in Theorem 15.

Suppose that $u, v \in \mathbb{N}$ and the public parameter $e < N$ satisfy at most one equation $eX - NY = (p^2u + q^2v)Z$ with $\gcd(X, (p^2u + q^2v)) = 1$. Observe that since $\gcd(X, Y)=1$, then reduce the equation to $e \equiv (p^2u + q^2v)ZX^{-1} \pmod{N}$. We describe the following lemma which show that different parameter X_1, X_2 define different exponents e_1, e_2 .

Lemma 11. [38] m and n be positive integers. Then

$$m \frac{\phi(n)}{n} - 2^{\omega(n)} < \sum_{k=1, \gcd(k,n)=1}^m 1 < m \frac{\phi(n)}{n} + 2^{\omega(n)}.$$

where $\omega(n)$ is the number of distinct prime factor of n .

Proof. Let $\mu(d)$ be the Möbius function which is defined by $\mu(1) = 1$, $\mu(d) = 0$ if d is not square-free and $\mu(d) = (-1)^{\omega(d)}$ where d is square-free where $\omega(d)$ is the number of distinct prime factors of d . Then, from Legendre Theorem gives

$$\sum_{k=1, \gcd(k,n)=1}^m 1 = \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) \lfloor \frac{m}{d} \rfloor.$$

Since $\lfloor \frac{m}{d} \rfloor \leq \frac{m}{d} < \lfloor \frac{m}{d} \rfloor + 1$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) \lfloor \frac{m}{d} \rfloor &= \sum_{d|n, \mu(d)=1} \mu(d) \lfloor \frac{m}{d} \rfloor + \sum_{d|n, \mu(d)=-1} \mu(d) \lfloor \frac{m}{d} \rfloor \\ &> \sum_{d|n, \mu(d)=1} \mu(d) \left(\frac{m}{d} - 1 \right) + \sum_{d|n, \mu(d)=-1} \mu(d) \frac{m}{d} \\ &= \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) \frac{m}{d} - \sum_{d|n, \mu(d)=1} 1 \\ &> m \sum_{d|n} \frac{\mu(d)}{d} - \sum_{d|n} |\mu(d)| \\ &= m \frac{\phi(n)}{n} - 2^{\omega(n)}. \end{aligned}$$

The Möbius function satisfies $\sum_{d|n} \frac{\mu(d)}{d} = \frac{\phi(n)}{n}$. (see 16.3.1 in [16]) It also satisfies $\sum_{d|n} |\mu(d)| = 2^{\omega(n)}$ ([16], Theorem 264). It follows that

$$\sum_{k=1, \gcd(k,n)=1}^m 1 > m \frac{\mu(n)}{n} - 2^{\omega(n)}.$$

On the other hand, using $\lfloor \frac{m}{d} \rfloor \leq \frac{m}{d} < \lfloor \frac{m}{d} \rfloor + 1$ we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) \lfloor \frac{m}{d} \rfloor &= \sum_{d|n, \mu(d)=1} \mu(d) \lfloor \frac{m}{d} \rfloor + \sum_{d|n, \mu(d)=-1} \mu(d) \lfloor \frac{m}{d} \rfloor \\ &< \sum_{d|n, \mu(d)=-1} \mu(d) \frac{m}{d} + \sum_{d|n, \mu(d)=1} \mu(d) \left(\frac{m}{d} - 1 \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) \frac{m}{d} - \sum_{d|n, \mu(d)=-1} 1 \\
&< m \sum_{d|n} \frac{\mu(d)}{d} + \sum_{d|n} |\mu(d)| \\
&= m \frac{\phi(n)}{n} + 2^{\omega(n)}.
\end{aligned}$$

□

Lemma 12. Let $N = p^2q$ be RSA modulus with $q < p < 2q$ and $u, v \in \mathbb{N}$. For $i = 1, 2$, let e_i be two exponents satisfying $eX_i - NY_i = (p^2u + q^2v)Z$ with $\gcd(X_i, (p^2u + q^2v)Z)$ and $X_i|Z| < \frac{N}{2|p^2u + q^2v|}$. Then $X_1 \neq X_2$ and $e_1 \neq e_2$.

Proof. Suppose that for $i = 1, 2$ and assume for contradiction that $e_1 = e_2$ and e satisfying

$$(p^2u + q^2v)ZX_1^{-1} \equiv (p^2u + q^2v)ZX_2^{-1} \pmod{N} \quad (3.2)$$

Rearrange (3.2), we obtain

$$(p^2u + q^2v)Z(X_1^{-1} - X_2^{-1}) \equiv 0 \pmod{N}.$$

Then, we notice that, since $\gcd(X_i, (p^2u + q^2v)Z)$, then $X_2^{-1} - X_1^{-1} \equiv 0 \pmod{N}$ and $X_2 - X_1 \equiv 0 \pmod{N}$. Then, we have

$$|X_2 - X_1| \leq X_2 + X_1 < 2 \left(\frac{N}{2(p^2u + q^2v)} \right) < N \quad (3.3)$$

Hence, $X_2 - X_1 = 0$ and $X_2 = X_1$. It follows that $e_1 = e_2$. □

Here, the following theorem shows the result estimation of the weak exponents e with the structure $e \equiv (p^2u + q^2v)X^{-1} \pmod{N}$ with $\gcd(X, (p^2u + q^2v)) = 1$ and $X < \frac{N}{2(p^2u + q^2v)}$ by applying Lemma 11 and Theorem 15 and we consider only for the case when $Z = 1$.

Theorem 16. Let $N = p^2q$ be RSA modulus with $q < p < 2q$ and $u, v \in \mathbb{N}$. The number of exponents e satisfying $e \equiv (p^2u + q^2v)X^{-1} \pmod{N}$ with $\gcd(X, (p^2u + q^2v)) = 1$ and $X < \frac{N}{2(p^2u + q^2v)}$ where $|p^2u + q^2v| = N^{\frac{1}{3} + \beta}$ is at least $N^{\frac{1}{3} + \beta}$, $\epsilon > 0$ is arbitrarily small for suitably large N .

Proof. Suppose the number of exponents satisfying

$$e \equiv (p^2u + q^2v)X^{-1} \pmod{N}$$

with the condition of the theorem is

$$N = \sum_{X=1, \gcd(X, p^2u + q^2v)=1}^{B_1} 1$$

. where

$$B_1 = \lfloor \frac{N}{2p^2u + q^2v} \rfloor.$$

Now, by using Lemma 11 with $n = p^2u + q^2v$ and $m = B_1$, we obtain

$$B_1 \frac{\phi(n)(p^2u + q^2v)}{p^2u + q^2v} - 2^{\omega(n)(p^2u + q^2v)} < N < B_1 \frac{\phi(n)(p^2u + q^2v)}{p^2u + q^2v} + 2^{\omega(n)(p^2u + q^2v)}. \quad (3.4)$$

Notice that, $2^{\omega(n)(p^2u + q^2v)}$ is the number of square free divisors of $p^2u + q^2v$ which is upper bounded by the total number $\pi p^2u + q^2v$ of divisors of $p^2u + q^2v$. Since $\pi(n)$ satisfies $\pi(n) = \log \log n$ ([16], Theorem 430-431).

Since $n = p^2u + q^2v = N^{\frac{2}{3} + \beta}$ and $B_1 = \lfloor \frac{N}{2(p^2u + q^2v)} \rfloor$, then $B_1 = \lfloor \frac{1}{2} N^{\frac{1}{3} - \beta} \rfloor$.

Hence, we obtain

$$\mathcal{N} = \frac{\phi(n)(p^2u + q^2v)}{p^2u + q^2v} = N^{-\frac{1}{3} - 2\beta} \phi(p^2u + q^2v). \quad (3.5)$$

By using ([16], Theorem 328)

$$\phi(n) > \frac{cn}{\log \log n} \quad . \quad (3.6)$$

Then, we substitute (3.6) in (3.5), we get

$$N = \frac{c \left(N^{\frac{2}{3} + \beta} \right)}{\log \log \left(N^{\frac{2}{3} + \beta} \right)} \times N^{-\frac{1}{3} - 2\beta} = N^{\frac{1}{3} - \beta - \epsilon}.$$

□

3.2 The Second Attack on k moduli $N_i = p_i^2 q_i$

We propose our second attack. Suppose that we are given k moduli $N_i = p_i^2 q_i$. We consider in this scenario that the following generalized system of key equation given by $e_i x - N_i y_i = (p_i^2 u + q_i^2 v) z_i$ will provide us the factor of each moduli which are all of the same size. We show that there, it is possible to factor k RSA moduli. This is achievable when the unknown parameters x, y_i and z_i are suitably small. We suitably couple this information to gather with the execution of the LLL algorithm to achieve our objective.

Theorem 17. *For $k \geq 2$, let $N_i = p_i^2 q_i$, $1 \leq i \leq k$ be k RSA moduli each with the same size N where $N = \min_i N_i$. Let e_i , $i = 1, \dots, k$ be k public exponents. Define $\delta = \frac{k}{6}$. Let $u, v \in \mathbb{N}$ such that u is an integer multiple of 2 and v is an integer multiple of 3. If there exists an integer $x < N^\delta$ and k integers $y_i < N^\delta$ and $|z_i| < \frac{\sqrt{2} N^{1/2}}{|p_i^2 u - q_i^2 v|}$ such that $e_i x - N_i y_i = (p_i^2 u + q_i^2 v) z_i$ for $i = 1, \dots, k$, then one can factor the k RSA moduli N_1, \dots, N_k in polynomial time .*

Proof. For $k \geq 2$ and $i = 1, \dots, k$, starting with the equation $e_i x - N_i y_i = (p_i^2 u + q_i^2 v) z_i$, we obtain

$$\left| \frac{e_i}{N_i} x - y_i \right| = \frac{|(p_i^2 u + q_i^2 v) z_i|}{N_i}. \quad (3.7)$$

Let $N = \min_i N_i$ and suppose that $y_i < N^\delta$ and $|z_i| < \frac{\sqrt{2} N^{1/2}}{|p_i^2 u - q_i^2 v|}$. We set $|p_i^2 u - q_i^2 v| > p_i$ since we use the relation $N^{1/3} < p < 2^{1/3} N^{1/3}$ and $p_i^2 u + q_i^2 v < 2N^{2/3}$ then we

will get

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{(p_i^2 u - q_i^2 v)|z_i|}{N_i} &\leq \frac{(p_i^2 u - q_i^2 v)|z_i|}{N} \\
&\leq \frac{\left(2N^{\frac{2}{3}}\right) \left(\frac{\sqrt{2}N^{1/2}}{N^{1/3}}\right)}{N} \\
&\leq \frac{2^{3/2} N^{5/6}}{N} \\
&= 2^{3/2} N^{-\frac{1}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Plugging (3.8) in (3.7), we obtain

$$\left| \frac{e_i}{N_i} x - y_i \right| \leq 2^{3/2} N^{-\frac{1}{6}}.$$

We now proceed to prove the existence of integer x . Let $\epsilon = 2^{3/2} N^{-\frac{1}{6}}$, $\delta = \frac{k}{6}$. We have

$$N^\delta \cdot \epsilon^k = 2^{\frac{3k}{2}} N^{\delta - \frac{k}{6}} = 2^{\frac{3k}{2}}.$$

Then, since $2^{\frac{3k}{2}} < 2^{\frac{k(k-3)}{4}} \cdot 3^k$ for $k \geq 2$, we get $N^\delta \cdot \epsilon^k < 2^{\frac{k(k-3)}{4}} \cdot 3^k$. It follows that if $x < N^\delta$, then $x < 2^{\frac{k(k-3)}{4}} \cdot 3^{-k}$. Summarizing for $i = 1, \dots, k$, we have

$$\left| \frac{e_i}{N_i} x - y_i \right| < \epsilon, x < 2^{\frac{k(k-3)}{4}} \cdot 3^k \cdot \epsilon^{-k}.$$

It follows the condition of Theorem 14 are fulfilled will find x and y_i for $i = 1, \dots, k$. Next, using the equation $e_i x - N_i y_i = (p_i^2 u + q_i^2 v) z_i$ and $1 < |z_i| < \frac{\sqrt{2}N^{1/2}}{|p_i^2 u - q_i^2 v|}$, this implies that $uvZ^2 q = \left[\frac{S^2}{4N} \right]$ for $S_i = e_i x_i - N_i y_i$ for each $i = 1, \dots, k$, we find $q_i = \gcd\left(\left[\frac{S^2}{4N_i} \right], N_i\right)$. This leads to the factorization of k RSA moduli N_1, \dots, N_k . \square

Example 2. As an illustration of this second attack, we consider the following three RSA moduli and public exponents

$$N_1 = 114000760222549864279781270853885152295461,$$

$$N_2 = 228115095149010518316554945466909090873661,$$

$$N_3 = 231236890212417970842411124690482829278481,$$

$$e_1 = 109098385125715102458611794533226114000584,$$

$$e_2 = 142008308621371178234527659441810463340520,$$

$$e_3 = 155000153884152408505814407363292624088474.$$

Then, $N = \min(N_1, N_2, N_3) = 114000760222549864279781270853885152295461$. Since $k = 3$, we get $\delta = \frac{k}{6} = \frac{1}{2}$ and $\epsilon = 2^{3/2} N^{-\frac{1}{6}} \approx 0.0000004061$. Set $u = 260$ and $v = 390$. then, by using (12) with $n = k = 3$, we find

$$C = \left[3^{n+1} 2^{\frac{(n+1)(n-1)}{4}} \epsilon^{-n-1} \right] = 1487807969515159755890958645.$$

Consider the lattice L spanned by the matrix

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -[Ce_1/N_1] & -[Ce_2/N_2] & -[Ce_3/N_3] \\ 0 & C & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & C & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C \end{bmatrix}.$$

Then, applying the LLL algorithm to L , we get a reduced basis with the matrix

$$K = \begin{bmatrix} -20928770380 & 18379710443495355 & 14570849265561705 & 14623041108483595 \\ -821694325288669743815 & -530766368893408117395 & 2473756275407667582000 & -1797809971033007371660 \\ 3954727165130615012467 & 763232605728921873804 & 152563492536187551627 & -1111295022726225808720 \\ 3366893382339493311163 & -6149573579215638802239 & 3072678888010902213063 & 4667676475378000743755 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Now, we obtain

$$KM^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} -20928770380 & -20028770393 & -13028770767 & -14028741809 \\ -821694325288669743815 & -786359001299235418497 & -511528714317654489673 & -550789049050439590568 \\ 3954727165130615012467 & 3784662018799447688318 & 2461933154455801268684 & 2650888958945896073772 \\ 3366893382339493311163 & 3222106854257955345071 & 2095989457524477103184 & 2256858721351764003931 \end{bmatrix}.$$

From the first row, we deduce $x = 20928770380, y_1 = 20028770393, y_2 = 13028770767$ and $y_3 = 14028741809$. By using x and y_i for $i = 1, 2, 3$ define $S_i = e_i x N_i y_i$ is an approximation of $p_i^2 u + q_i^2 v$. Hence, by using Lemma 9 and Theorem 15, this implies that $wvZ^2 = \left\lfloor \frac{S_i^2}{4N_i} \right\rfloor$ for $S_i = e_i x N_i y_i$. Then, we obtain

$$S_1 = 1408315151419853220300456815747,$$

$$S_2 = 2234046567945829713849902729613,$$

$$S_3 = 2272731290043918799693441887991.$$

Then, for each $i = 1, 2, 3$, we find $\left\lfloor \frac{S_i^2}{4N_i} \right\rfloor$ and we obtain

$$\left\lfloor \frac{S_1^2}{4N_1} \right\rfloor = 4349426183314188600, \left\lfloor \frac{S_2^2}{4N_2} \right\rfloor = 5469787153377900600,$$

$$\left\lfloor \frac{S_3^2}{4N_3} \right\rfloor = 5584432821250709400.$$

For each $i = 1, 2, 3$, we find $q_i = \gcd\left(\left\lfloor \frac{S_i^2}{4N_i} \right\rfloor, N_i\right)$ and we obtain

$$q_1 = 42893749342349, q_2 = 53942674096429, q_3 = 55073301984721.$$

This leads us to the factorization of three RSA moduli N_1, N_2 and N_3 which

$$p_1 = 51553347319883, p_2 = 65029554162953, p_3 = 64797462962081.$$

3.3 The Third Attack on k moduli $N_i = p_i^2 q_i$

We propose our third attack. Suppose that we are given k moduli $N_i = p_i^2 q_i$. We consider in this scenario that the following generalized system of key equation given by $e_i x_i N_i y_i = (p_i^2 u + q_i^2 v) z_i$ will provide us the factor of each moduli which are all of the same size. We show that there, it is possible to factor k RSA moduli. This is achievable when the unknown parameters x_i, y and z_i are suitably small. We

couple this information together with the execution of the LLL algorithm to achieve our objective.

Theorem 18. For $k \geq 2$, let $N_i = p_i^2 q_i$, $1 \leq i \leq k$ be k RSA moduli each with the same size N where $N = \max_i N_i$. Let e_i , $i = 1, \dots, k$ be k public exponents with $\min_i e_i = N^\beta$. Define $\delta = \beta k - \frac{5k}{6}$. Let $u, v \in \mathbb{N}$ such that u is an integer multiple of 2 and v is an integer multiple of 3. If there exists an integer $y < N^\delta$, k integers $x_i < N^\delta$ and $|z_i| < \frac{\sqrt{2}N^{1/2}}{|p_i^2 u - q_i^2 v|}$ such that $e_i x_i - N_i y = (p_i^2 u + q_i^2 v) z_i$ for $i = 1, \dots, k$, then one can factor the k RSA moduli N_1, \dots, N_k in polynomial time.

Proof. For $k \geq 2$ and $i = 1, \dots, k$, the equation $e_i x_i - N_i y = (p_i^2 u + q_i^2 v) z_i$, we get

$$\left| \frac{N_i}{e_i} y - x_i \right| = \frac{|(p_i^2 u + q_i^2 v) z_i|}{e_i} \quad (3.8)$$

Let $N = \max_i N_i$ and suppose that $y < N^\delta$, $|z_i| < \frac{\sqrt{2}N^{1/2}}{|p_i^2 u - q_i^2 v|}$ and $\min_i e_i = N^\beta$. We set $|p_i^2 u + q_i^2 v| > p_i$ since we use the relation $N^{1/3} < p < 2^{1/3} N^{1/3}$ and $p_i^2 u + q_i^2 v < 2N^{2/3}$ then we will get

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{|(p_i^2 u + q_i^2 v) z_i|}{e_i} &\leq \frac{(p_i^2 u + q_i^2 v) |z_i|}{N^\beta} \\ &< \frac{(2N^{2/3}) \frac{\sqrt{2}N^{1/2}}{|p_i^2 u - q_i^2 v|}}{N^\beta} \\ &< \frac{(2N^{2/3}) \frac{\sqrt{2}N^{1/2}}{N^{1/3}}}{N^\beta} \\ &= 2^{\frac{2}{3}} N^{\frac{5}{6} - \beta} \end{aligned}$$

Plugging (3.9) in (3.8), we obtain

$$\left| \frac{N_i}{e_i} y - x_i \right| < 2^{\frac{2}{3}} N^{\frac{5}{6} - \beta}.$$

We now proceed to prove the existence of integer y and the integers x_i . Let $\epsilon =$

$2^{\frac{2}{3}} N^{\frac{5}{6}-\beta}$, $\delta = \beta k - \frac{5k}{6}$. Then, we obtain

$$N^\delta \epsilon^k = N^\delta (2^{\frac{2}{3}} N^{\frac{5}{6}-\beta})^k = 2^{\frac{3k}{2}} (N^{\delta + \frac{5}{6}k - \beta k}) = 2^{\frac{3}{2}} k.$$

Then, since $2^{\frac{3}{2}} < 2^{\frac{k(k-3)}{4}} 3^k$ for $k \geq 2$, we get $N^\delta \epsilon^k < 2^{\frac{k(k-3)}{4}} 3^k$. It follows that if $y < N^\delta$, then $y < 2^{\frac{k(k-3)}{4}} 3^k \epsilon^{-k}$. Summarizing for $i = 1, \dots, k$, we get

$$|\frac{N_i}{e_i} y - x_i| < \epsilon, y < 2^{\frac{k(k-3)}{4}} 3^k \epsilon^{-k}, \text{ for } i = 1, \dots, k,$$

It follows the condition of Theorem 14 are fulfilled will find y and x_i for $i = 1, \dots, k$. Next, by using the equation $e_i x_i N_i y = (p_i^2 u + q_i^2 v) z_i$ and since $1 < |z_i| < \frac{\sqrt{2} N^{1/2}}{|p_i^2 u - q_i^2 v|}$ and this implies that $uvZ_2q = (\left[\frac{S_i^2}{4N_i} \right], N_i)$. This leads to the factorization of k RSA moduli N_1, \dots, N_k . \square

Example 3. As an illustration of the third attack, consider the following three RSA moduli and public exponents

$$N_1 = 147314237626225897112311813588154268426541,$$

$$N_2 = 237775916900172954272543791107506089080583,$$

$$N_3 = 339469256280126448305842424969023615121683,$$

$$e_1 = 114870922237709588771245579061028359832082,$$

$$e_2 = 190060878414430430558257488372807936044696,$$

$$e_3 = 285683325696348235446830296205564009730629.$$

$$\text{Then } N = \max(N_1, N_2, N_3) = 339469256280126448305842424969023615121683.$$

We also obtain $\min(e_1, e_2, e_3) = N^\beta$ with $\beta \approx 0.9886688835$. Since $k = 3$ we get $\delta = \beta k - \frac{5k}{6} = 0.466006650$ and $\epsilon = 2^{\frac{2}{3}} N^{\frac{5}{6}-\beta} \approx .0000010007$. Set $u = 300$ and $v = 450$. Then, by using (12) with $n = k = 3$, we find

$$C = \left[3^{n+1} 2^{\frac{(n+1)(n-1)}{4}} \epsilon^{-n-1} \right] = 40375135744077325436700551.$$

Consider the lattice L spanned by the matrix

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -[Ce_1/N_1] & -[Ce_2/N_2] & -[Ce_3/N_3] \\ 0 & C & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & C & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C \end{bmatrix}.$$

Then, applying the LLL algorithm to L , we get a reduced basis with the matrix

$$K = \begin{bmatrix} -3186595759 & -666654400396680 & -538317459032548 & -502459761727128 \\ -80004816082475565419 & -256706228905171710597 & 186745528335567423374 & 140520570411343159128 \\ -384981563884386646447 & -58239693649250278240 & 37246015231993662609 & 37369006403280349418 \\ -137762503349110575602 & -40146208250920113708 & 383386780152511327889 & -357481563550077921439 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$KM^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} -3186595759 & -4086594899 & -3986594899 & -3786539833 \\ -80004816082475565419 & -102600799732652192026 & -100090132483550528817 & -95067415461319812077 \\ -384981563884386646447 & 493712982180297031867 & -481631701936416978224 & -45746248877087775947 \\ -137762503349110575602 & -176671151924402499790 & -172347964618324415739 & -163699209399846282679 \end{bmatrix}.$$

From the first row, we deduce $y = 3186595759$, $x_1 = 4086594899$, $x_2 = 3986594899$ and $x_3 = 3786539833$. By using y and x_i for $i = 1, 2, 3$, define $S_i = e_i x_i N_i y$ is an approximation of $p_i^2 u + q_i^2 v$. Hence, by using Lemma 9 and Theorem 15, this implies that $wvZ^2q = \left\lceil \frac{S_i^2}{4N} \right\rceil$ for $S_i = e_i x_i N_i y$. Then, we get

$$S_1 = 1896689401488740578359644110099,$$

$$S_2 = 2534050590627111611641312558207,$$

$$S_3 = 3555263844990520758622991902560.$$

Next, for each $i = 1, 2, 3$, we find $\left\lceil \frac{S_i^2}{4N_i} \right\rceil$ and we get $\left\lceil \frac{S_1^2}{4N_1} \right\rceil = 6105028854792915000$, $\left\lceil \frac{S_2^2}{4N_2} \right\rceil = 6751537833995145000$, $\left\lceil \frac{S_3^2}{4N_3} \right\rceil = 9308575646881605000$. For each $i = 1, 2, 3$, we find $q_i = \gcd\left(\left\lceil \frac{S_i^2}{4N_i} \right\rceil, N_i\right)$ and we obtain

$$q_1 = 45222435961429, q_2 = 50011391362927, q_3 = 68952412199123.$$

This leads us to the factorization of three RSA moduli N_1, N_2 and N_3 which

$$p_1 = 57074929677173, p_2 = 68952412199123, p_3 = 70165801822561.$$

Chapter 4

RSA with modulus $N = p^r q$

In [46] *Takagi* showed how to use the Prime Power RSA to speed up the decryption process when the public and private exponents satisfy an equation $ed \equiv 1 \pmod{(p-1)(q-1)}$. As in the standard RSA Cryptosystem, the security of the Prime Power RSA depends on the difficulty of factoring integers of the form $N = p^r q$. In this chapter, we focus on the Prime Power RSA with a modulus $N = p^r q$, and present three new attacks:

In the first attack, we consider a public exponent e satisfying an equation $ex - \phi(N)y = z$ where x and y are positive integers. Unlike *Sarkar* who solves $ex - \phi(N)k = 1$, we solve a more general equation $ex - \phi(N)k = z$. This leads to less constraints on the solution space, which in turn leads to an increase in the number of solutions to the equation.

In the second attack, we consider an instance of the Prime Power RSA with modulus $N = p^r q$. We show that one can factor N if two private keys d_1 and d_2 share an amount of their most significant bits, that is if $|d_1 - d_2|$ is small enough. More precisely, we show that if $|d_1 - d_2| < N^{\frac{r(r-1)}{(r+1)^2}}$, then N can be factored in polynomial

time.

In the third attack, we consider two instances of the Prime Power RSA with two moduli $N_1 = p_1^r q_1$ and $N_2 = p_2^r q_2$ such that the prime factors p_1 and p_2 share an amount of their most significant bits, that is $|p_1 - p_2|$ is small. More precisely, we show that one can factor the RSA moduli N_1 and N_2 in polynomial time if $|p_1 - p_2| < \frac{p_1}{2rq_1q_2}$. The method we use for this attack is based on the continued fraction algorithm.

Theorem 19. (Lu, Zhang and Lin) *Let N be a composite integer with a divisor p^u such that $p \geq N^\beta$ for some $0 < \beta \leq 1$. Let $f(x, y) \in \mathbb{Z}[x, y]$ be a homogenous linear polynomial. Then one can find all the solutions (x, y) of the equation $f(x, y) = 0 \pmod{p^u}$ with $\gcd(x, y) = 1$, $|x| < N^{\gamma_1}$, $|y| < N_2^{\gamma_2}$, in polynomial time if $\gamma_1 + \gamma_2 < uv\beta^2$.*

4.1 The First Attack on Prime Power RSA with modulus $N = p^r q$

We present an attack on the Prime Power RSA when the public key (N, e) satisfies an equation $ed - \phi(N)k = z$ with small parameters d and $|z|$.

Theorem 20. *Let $N = p^r q$ be a Prime Power RSA modulus and e a public exponent satisfying the equation $ex - \phi(N)y = z$ with $y \neq 0 \pmod{pq}$, $1 < e < \phi(N)$ and $\gcd(e, \phi(N)) = 1$. Then one can factor N in polynomial time if*

$$|xy| < N^{\frac{r(r-1)}{(r+1)^2}}.$$

Proof. Suppose that $e < N$ satisfies an equation $ex - \phi(N)y = z$ with $|x| < N^\delta$ and

$|z| < N^\gamma$. Then, since $\phi(N) = p^{r-1}(p-1)(q-1)$, we get $ex - z = 0 \pmod{p^{r-1}}$. Applying Theorem 19 with $u = r, v = r-1$ and $\beta = \frac{1}{r+1}$, we can solve the equation in polynomial time if

$$\delta + \gamma < uv\beta^2 = \frac{r(r-1)}{(r+1)^2}$$

that is $|xz| < N^{\frac{r(r-1)}{(r+1)^2}}$. Since $\frac{e}{\phi(N)} < 1$, then, using x and z in the equation $ex - \phi(N)y = z$, we get for sufficiently large N comparatively to r ,

$$\begin{aligned} y = \frac{ex - z}{\phi(N)} &< \frac{e|x|}{\phi(N)} + \frac{|z|}{\phi(N)} \\ &< |x| + |z| \\ &\leq 1 + |xz| \\ &< 1 + N^{\frac{r(r-1)}{(r+1)^2}} \\ &< N. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, when $y \neq 0 \pmod{pq}$, we get

$$\gcd(ex - z, N) = \gcd(p^{r-1}(p-1)(q-1)k, p^r q) = g,$$

with $g = p^{r-1}, g = p^r$ or $g = p^{r-1}q$. If $g = p^{r-1}$, then $p = g^{\frac{1}{r-1}}$, if $g = p^r$, then $p = g^{\frac{1}{r}}$ and if $g = p^{r-1}q$, then $p = \frac{N}{g}$. This leads to the factorization of N . \square

Example 4. For $r = 2$ and $N = p^r q$, let us take for N and e the 55 digit numbers

$$N = 8138044578297117319482018441148072252199996769522371021$$

$$e = 1199995230601021126201343651611107957480251354355883029.$$

In order to solve the diophantine equation $ex - \phi(N)y = z$, we transformed it into the equation $ex - z \equiv 0 \pmod{p^{r-1}}$ using theorem 20. To apply Coppersmiths technique via Theorem 19, we choose the parameters $m = 7, t = 6$ so that the dimension of

constructed the lattice is 36, and $X = \left\lceil N^{\frac{r(r-1)}{(r+1)^2}} \right\rceil = 1592999974064$. We built the lattice using the polynomial $f(x_1, x_2) = x_1 + ex_2$, then applied the LLL algorithm [29], and used Gröbner basis method to find the smallest solution $x_1 = -11537$ and $x_2 = 7053$ to $f(x_1, x_2) \equiv 0 \pmod{p^{r-1}}$ in 174 seconds using an off-the-shelf computer. From this solution, we deduced $p = \gcd(x_1 + ex_2, N) = 2294269585934949239$, and finally recovered $q = \frac{N}{p^2} = 1546077175000723901$. We then computed $\phi(N)$ and $d \equiv e^{-1} \pmod{\phi(N)}$ as follows:

$$\phi(N) = 8138044578297117310671227668089561946257896925261579800,$$

$$d = 2015994747748388772982436393811213317361971865510756269.$$

Observe that $d \approx N^{.98}$ which is out of range of Sarkar's bound [45] which can only retrieve private keys $d < N^{.395}$ for $r = 2$.

4.2 The Second Attack on Prime Power RSA using Two Decryption Exponents

We present an attack on the Prime Power RSA when two private exponents d_1 and d_2 share an amount of their most significant bits, that is $|d_1 - d_2|$ is small.

Theorem 21. *Let $N = p^r q$ be an RSA modulus and d_1 and d_2 be two private exponents such that $e_1 e_2 (d_1 - d_2) - (e_2 - e_1) \not\equiv 0 \pmod{N}$. Then, one can factor N in polynomial time, if*

$$|d_1 - d_2| < N^{\frac{r(r-1)}{(r+1)^2}}.$$

Proof. Suppose that $e_1 d_1 - k_1 \phi(N) = 1$ and $e_2 d_2 - k \phi(N) = 1$ with $e_1 > e_2$. Hence $e_1 d_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{\phi(N)}$ and $e_2 d_2 \equiv 1 \pmod{\phi(N)}$. Multiplying the first equations by

e_2 and the second by e_1 and subtracting, we get

$$e_1 e_2 (d_1 - d_2) \equiv e_2 - e_1 \pmod{\phi(N)}.$$

Since $\phi(N) = p^{r-1}(p-1)(q-1)$, we get $e_1 e_2 (d_1 - d_2) \equiv e_2 - e_1 \pmod{p^{r-1}}$. Now, consider the modular linear equation

$$e_1 e_2 x - (e_2 - e_1) \equiv 0 \pmod{p^{r-1}},$$

$d_1 - d_2$ is a root of such equation. Suppose further that $|d_1 - d_2| < N^\delta$, then applying Theorem 19 with $u = r$, $v = r - 1$ and $\beta = \frac{1}{r+1}$ will lead to the solution $x = d_1 - d_2$ obtained in polynomial time if

$$\delta < uv\beta^2 = \frac{r(r-1)}{(r+1)^2}.$$

That is if $|d_1 - d_2| < N^{\frac{r(r-1)}{(r+1)^2}}$. Computing $\gcd(e_1 e_2 x - (e_2 - e_1), N) = \gcd(p^{r-1}(p-1)(q-1)y, p^r q) = g$, and assuming that $e_1 e_2 (d_1 - d_2) - (e_2 - e_1) \not\equiv 0 \pmod{N}$ will lead to determining p , hence factoring N as follows: $p = g^{\frac{1}{r-1}}$ when $g = p^{r-1}$, or $p = g^{\frac{1}{r}}$ when $g = p^r$, or $p = \frac{N}{g}$ if $g = p^{r-1}q$. \square

Example 5. Let us present an example corresponding to Theorem . Consider $N = p^2q$ with

$$N = 6093253851486120878859471958399737725885946526553626219$$

$$e_1 = 2749600381847487389715964767235618802529675855606377411$$

$$e_2 = 3575081244952414009316396501512372226545892558898276551.$$

The polynomial equation is $f(x) = e_1 e_2 x - (e_2 - e_1) \equiv 0 \pmod{p^{r-1}}$, which can be transformed into $g(x) = x - 1 = 0 \pmod{p^{r-1}}$ where $a \equiv (e_2 - e_1)(e_1 e_2)^{-1} \pmod{N}$. Using $m = 8$ and $t = 6$, we built a lattice with dimension $\omega = 9$. Applying the LLL algorithm [29] and solving the first reduced polynomials, we get the solution

$x_0 = 1826732340$. Hence $\gcd(f(x_0), N) = p = 1789386140116417697$ and finally $q = \frac{N}{p^2} = 1903010275819064491$. The whole process took less than 4 seconds using an off-shelf computer. Then, using $\phi(N) = p(p-1)(q-1)$, we retried the private exponents $d_1 \equiv e_1^{-1} \pmod{\phi(N)}$ and $d_2 \equiv e_2^{-1} \pmod{\phi(N)}$. Note that again $d_1 \approx d_2 \approx N^{0.99}$ which sarkar's method with the bound $d < N^{.395}$ could not possibly retrieve.

4.3 The Third Attack on Prime Power RSA with Two RSA moduli

We consider two Prime Power RSA moduli $N_1 = p_1^r q_1$ and $N_2 = p_2^r q_2$, where p_1 and p_2 share an amount of their most significant bits.

Theorem 22. *Let $N_1 = p_1^r q_1$ and $N_2 = p_2^r q_2$ be two RSA moduli with $p_1 > p_2$. If*

$$|p_1 - p_2| < \frac{p_1}{2r q_1 q_2},$$

then, one can factor N in polynomial time.

Proof. Suppose that $N_1 = p_1^r q_1$ and $N_2 = p_2^r q_2$ with $p_1 > p_2$. Then $q_2 N_1 - q_1 N_2 = q_1 q_2 (p_1^r - p_2^r)$. Hence

$$\left| \frac{N_2}{N_1} - \frac{q_2}{q_1} \right| = \frac{q_1 q_2 |p_1^r - p_2^r|}{q_1^2 p_1^r}.$$

In order to apply Theorem 1, we need that $\frac{q_1 q_2 |p_1^r - p_2^r|}{q_1^2 p_1^r} < \frac{1}{2q_1^2}$, or equivalently

$$|p_1^r - p_2^r| < \frac{p_1^r}{2q_1 q_2}. \quad (4.1)$$

Observe that

$$|p_1^r - p_2^r| = |p_1 - p_2| \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} p_1^{r-1-i} p_2^i < r |p_1 - p_2| p_1^{r-1}. \quad (4.2)$$

Then 4.1 is fulfilled if $r|p_1 - p_2|p_1^{r-1} < \frac{p_1^r}{2q_1q_2}$, that is if

$$|p_1 - p_2| < \frac{p_1}{2rq_1q_2}.$$

Under this condition, we get $\frac{q_2}{q_1}$ among the convergence of the continued fraction expansion of $\frac{N_2}{N_1}$. Using q_1 and q_2 , we get $p_1 = \left(\frac{N_1}{q_1}\right)^{\frac{1}{r}}$ and $p_2 = \left(\frac{N_2}{q_2}\right)^{\frac{1}{r}}$. \square

Example 6. We present here an example corresponding to Theorem. Consider $N_1 = p_1^2q_1$ and $N_2 = p_2^2q_2$ with

$$N_1 = 170987233913769420505896917437304719816691353833034482461$$

$$N_2 = 120532911819726882881630714003135237766675602824250965921.$$

We applied the continued fraction algorithm to compute the first 40 convergence of $\frac{N_2}{N_1}$. Every convergent is a candidate for the ratio $\frac{q_2}{q_1}$ of the prime factors. One of the convergence is $\frac{36443689}{51698789}$ leading to $q_2 = 36443689$ and $q_1 = 51698789$. This gives the prime factors p_1 and p_2

$$p_1 = \sqrt{\frac{N_1}{q_1}} = 1818618724382942951460443$$

$$p_2 = \sqrt{\frac{N_2}{q_2}} = 1818618724382943035672683.$$

Chapter 5

Conclusion

We have examined the RSA Cryptosystem, the most widely deployed public-key cryptosystem. We have also studied various cryptanalytic attacks on RSA. Specifically, we contributed the following to the field of the RSA Cryptosystem study:

- We described the main schemes of RSA, namely key generation, encryption and decryption.
- We provided a detailed survey of the mathematical algebraic tools that are used in the principal attacks on RSA. This includes fractions and the basic theory of lattices and the LLL algorithm for basis reduction.
- We presented new attacks on RSA and revisited various old ones that are based on Diophantine approximations, lattice reduction and Coppersmith's techniques for solving modular equations.

The effectiveness of the proposed attacks is optimized for instances of RSA with small private exponents or public exponents satisfying some specific equations. These results illustrate once again the fact that the crypto-designer

should be very cautious when using RSA with such secret exponents.

In this thesis we presented new attacks on RSA moduli type $N = p^2q$. The attack is based on the equation $eX - NY = (p^2u + q^2v)Z$ where u is an integer multiple of 2 and v is an integer multiple of 3 together with some conditions on the parameters. Continuing our work, we focused on the system of generalised key equations of the form of $e_i x_i - N_i y_i = (p_i^2 u + q_i^2 v) z_i$ for the second attack and in the form of $e_i x_i - N_i y_i = (p_i^2 u + q_i^2 v) z_i$ for the third attack. We have proved the two attacks are successful when the parameters x_i, y_i and z_i are suitably small. On top of that, we also proved that both of our attacks enables us to factor k RSA moduli of the form $N_i = p_i^2 q_i$ simultaneously based on LLL algorithm. we have considered the Prime Power RSA with modulus $N = p^r q$ and public exponent e . The attack can be applied if small parameters x, y and z satisfying the equation $ex - \phi(N)y = z$ can be found.

We have considered the Prime Power RSA with modulus $N = p^r q$ and public exponent e . We presented three new attacks to factor the modulus in polynomial time. The first attack can be applied if small parameters x, y and z satisfying the equation $ex - \phi(N)y = z$ can be found. The second attack can be applied when two private exponents d_1 and d_2 share an amount of their most significant bits. The third attack can be applied when two Prime Power RSA moduli $N_1 = p_1^r q_1$ and $N_2 = p_2^r q_2$ are such that p_1 and p_2 share an amount of their most significant bits.

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